
D3.3 Analysis of new scales and KPIs

Task 3.2 Analysis of new scales and KPIs

WP3 Deriving Technical Guidelines for EPCs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report on the Analysis of New Scales and KPIs for Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) presents a comprehensive assessment of the latest Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aimed at improving the accuracy, reliability, and relevance of energy performance evaluations. This document examines KPIs across several dimensions, including Smartness, Human-Centric factors, Energy Performance, Financial aspects, and Climate Change impacts, while also reviewing related KPIs from other Horizon 2020 projects.

Key findings reveal that European projects predominantly focus on Smartness and Energy Performance indicators. Notably, the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) stands out as a critical metric introduced to enhance energy efficiency and promote market adoption of smart-ready technologies. This indicator addresses key functionalities such as energy optimization, user responsiveness, and grid interaction. Furthermore, the SRI aims to foster investment in advanced building technologies by establishing a standardized framework for comparing smart-ready services.

In terms of Energy Performance, indicators evaluating energy efficiency, real-time consumption, and energy demand forecasts are increasingly being integrated into EPC methodologies. These metrics provide crucial insights into energy usage patterns, enhance monitoring accuracy, and support the development of more effective energy-saving strategies.

Human-Centric KPIs emphasize improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), which encompasses indoor air quality, thermal comfort, visual comfort, and acoustic comfort. These indicators aim to promote occupant well-being and productivity, making buildings more liveable and adaptable to the diverse needs of users.

Financial indicators, including cost analysis, value determination, and risk assessment, are essential components for enhancing user awareness and guiding renovation decisions. Effective financial metrics help stakeholders evaluate the economic benefits of energy-efficient measures and encourage investments in building improvements.

Climate Change-related KPIs focus on assessing buildings' environmental impacts, primarily through the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable practices. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies and alignment with the European Level(s) framework are emphasized as key strategies for advancing sustainability goals.

The analysis also includes an extensive review of KPIs applied by various partner countries such as Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK (Scotland). It highlights that all these countries integrate Energy Performance indicators in their EPC frameworks, showcasing a broad consensus on the importance of energy efficiency metrics.

The main recommendation from the analysis is to adopt a holistic approach that combines all five KPI categories - energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, comfort, intelligence and financing - into a unified EPC framework. It is important to ensure that the end user can understand the indicators, so it is also recommended that the EPC template be adapted to include descriptions or a guide of the KPIs. Providing users with a comprehensive assessment is key to ensuring that the EPC conveys full knowledge of a building's performance, rather than fragmentary information.

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1 Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of energy efficiency and sustainable practices, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) have emerged as pivotal tools for assessing and communicating the energy efficiency of buildings. As the world grapples with the challenges of climate change and the imperative to transition towards greener infrastructures, the need for accurate and comprehensive metrics to evaluate energy performance becomes increasingly crucial.

This analysis delves into the realm of EPCs, shedding light on the latest advancements in scales and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) designed to enhance the precision and relevance of energy performance assessments. With a focus on innovation and adaptability, this report seeks to unravel the complexities associated with traditional metrics, presenting a comprehensive overview of the landscape in the field of building energy efficiency.

D3.3 will take existing EPC approaches of member states, alongside some alternative methods in D3.2,D2.3, WP5 , and propose a series of appropriate output metrics and KPIs that are deemed achievable from those methods (where some of these metrics may already be used by those methodologies). This mapping of appropriate output metrics with assessment type will then be used to highlight which type of approach is suitable for meeting “new” requirements of EPCs, and the degree to which such assessment approaches may be harmonized across member states.

In this report, KPIs are divided into five categories and a specific colour has been assigned:

Table 1 Categories and colours of KPIs

Smartness (yellow)
Human-Centric (blue)
Energy performance (green)
Financial (pink)
Climate change (red)

For statistical purposes, all KPIs listed from Horizon 2020 projects and partner countries have been tabulated and categories have been assigned to them to draw conclusions.

2 Identification of KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are metrics used to assess and measure various aspects of a building's performance, efficiency, and functionality. These indicators help building owners, facility managers, and stakeholders evaluate how well a building is meeting its objectives and identify areas for improvement. KPIs can be both qualitative and quantitative. Down below there are distinguished most commonly occurring KPIs among the projects and certificates.

2.1 Smartness

The SRI scheme is defined in Directive (EU) 2018/844, an amendment to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2010/31/EU and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) 2012/27/EU. It seeks to assess a building's capacity to align its operations with occupants' preferences and grid requirements, thus enhancing energy efficiency. SRI development has been triggered by the recast EPBD phasing out physical routine inspections of technical building systems (TBS) and introducing building automation and control systems (BACS) in their place. This shift is supported by regulations mandating room temperature controls and standardized building operating conditions.

Within the SRI framework, innovative technologies are leveraged to enhance energy performance and support the decarbonization of buildings. Provisions in the revised EPBD building codes align with the SRI methodology, particularly in the initial phases of implementing built-in electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. According to Directive 2014/94/EU, non-residential buildings undergoing new construction or renovation with more than 10 parking spaces must install ducting infrastructure for electric cables, allowing for the future installation of recharging points. This infrastructure also offers an opportunity to use car batteries as a power source¹. The provisions in the revised EPBD indicate a continuous expansion of the SRI scope in terms of smart-ready services, assessed domains, and building types. The SRI seeks to stimulate market demand and supply for competitive and capable smart-ready technologies (SRT) and services. By doing so, it aims to encourage investment in more intelligent buildings and building system technologies. The recast EPBD also obligates new buildings or those with new sources of heat to use self-regulating devices for temperature control in various zones or rooms. The SRI aims to provide a rating or indicator that reflects how "smart" a building is in terms of its ability to optimize energy performance, respond to user needs, and interact with energy grids. The criteria for assessing smart readiness encompass a range of factors, including the building's ability to adjust its operations based on occupant preferences, its integration with smart technologies, and its overall energy efficiency. Its goal is to prompt improvements through smart-ready services, raising awareness of advanced technologies among end-users as well as market participants. The SRI scheme prioritizes building energy performance, responsiveness to user needs, and energy demand flexibility as its three key functionalities². Despite the availability of building management systems (BMS), sustainability aspects like material use and unrelated smart technologies (e.g., security systems) are excluded from SRI domains.

Facility managers utilizing the SRI, and demonstrating energy and cost savings following SRI recommendations, have the potential to influence investor decisions towards adopting SRTs and long-term operation strategies, including deep energy efficiency renovations. In the smart home technologies market, the SRI engages service providers, such as network operators, technical building system manufacturers, and engineering firms, to position their service offerings competitively within a neutral and standardized framework. This approach allows consumers to more easily compare the capabilities of smart services, fostering a more attractive, affordable, and credible market. As consumer demand for improved functionality in smart-ready services increases, manufacturers are compelled to produce products with higher SRI labels, contributing to the rapid evolution of the technological

¹ 'Council Directive 2018/844' of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, May 2018

² Final report on the technical support to the development of a smart readiness indicator for buildings, VITO NV and Waide Strategic Efficiency Europe, June 2020

environment. Additionally, the financial market for energy efficiency experiences stimulation, leading to simultaneous growth in uptake and market expansion.

Many smart ready services are based on international technical standards and are categorised under 9 domains:

- heating,
- cooling,
- domestic hot water,
- ventilation,
- lighting,
- dynamic building envelope,
- electricity,
- EV charging,
- monitoring and control.

At least 2 and up to 5 functionality levels are defined for each service. A higher functionality level corresponds to a smarter level of implementation of the service. Disaggregated, the impact criteria include:

1. Specific energy savings on-site resulting from SRTs;
2. Flexibility for the grid and storage offered by smart ready services for district heating and cooling grids as well;
3. The comfort of the building user through conscious or unconscious perception of their indoor thermal environment;
4. Convenience in how easily the occupant interacts with the services in order to achieve ideal comfort levels;
5. Wellbeing and health impacts on users by the services;
6. Maintenance and fault prediction can potentially improve building energy performance by smart ready services automatically diagnosing inefficient operation;
7. Information to occupants on the status of the building's operations delivered by the smart ready services.

2.2 Human-Centric

Human-Centric Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are a transformative framework that redefines success in the building sector by measuring and prioritizing the well-being, satisfaction, and productivity of the individuals who inhabit these spaces. Traditionally, KPIs in the building sector have primarily revolved around factors such as energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental impact. While these metrics remain integral, the evolution towards human-centric considerations represents a more holistic approach that places humans at the core of design, construction, and operation. Recognizing that buildings are not just structures, but living ecosystems where people spend a sizeable portion of their lives, this approach places emphasis on how the built environment directly influences the quality of life for occupants. Human-centric KPIs extend beyond quantitative measures and focus on the qualitative aspects of the user experience within buildings. Descriptions of human-centric indicators are mainly in the EN 16798-1:2019³ standard, they cover factors such as indoor air quality, natural lighting, acoustics, thermal comfort, and ergonomic design—all of which contribute to the overall well-being of individuals within the space. Additionally, these indicators encapsulate the adaptability and flexibility of spaces to meet the diverse needs of the occupants.

³ EN 16798-1:2019 Energy performance of buildings - Ventilation for buildings - Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics

2.2.1 Indoor environment quality

The concept of Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) refers to the standard of indoor conditions within a building, intricately tied to human comfort and well-being. The collective IEQ of a building is shaped by diverse factors such as: indoor air quality (IAQ), thermal, visual, and acoustic comfort and spatial ergonomics. Moreover, this indicator is still evolving with new other considerations that have emerged in connection with IEQ – including water quality, electromagnetic radiation, and hygiene.

2.2.1.1 Acoustic comfort

Acoustic comfort refers to the level of sound quality within a building and the extent to how well it aligns with the desires and requirements of its inhabitants. Subpar acoustic conditions may result in diminished productivity, heightened stress levels and even negative health effects.

Excessive noise causes distraction and annoyance, it also hinders students' ability to understand speech, thereby impacting their learning outcomes. Noise in healthcare facilities has been shown to elevate patients' stress levels and impede their recovery process. In open-plan offices with inadequate acoustic conditions, employees may struggle to maintain concentration and productivity levels. These instances highlight the importance for architects and engineers to include acoustic comfort in their building designs. Through the strategic use of materials, layouts, and technologies, they can effectively mitigate the adverse effects of noise and craft environments that promote occupants' well-being and optimize performance. Here are some key factors to consider:

- **Sound Insulation:**
Effective sound insulation is vital to minimize the transfer of noise from one part of the building to another. Including features such as double-glazed windows, insulated walls, and acoustic ceiling systems can significantly reduce noise transmission, creating quieter and more peaceful indoor environments.
- **Room Acoustics:**
The acoustic properties of individual rooms impact the overall sound quality within a building. By employing sound-absorbing materials, such as acoustic panels or ceiling tiles, architects can control reverberation and improve speech intelligibility in spaces like auditoriums, classrooms, or conference rooms.
- **HVAC Systems:**
Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems are essential for maintaining optimal indoor temperatures and air quality. However, these systems can generate significant noise. By carefully selecting quiet and efficient HVAC equipment and designing ductwork properly, architects can mitigate excessive noise levels without compromising system functionality.

2.2.1.2 Thermal comfort

Thermal comfort is defined as the level of personal satisfaction with the existing thermal conditions. Perceived conditions significantly influence the mood and productivity of occupants in both residential and commercial spaces. Maintaining a comfortable internal environment additionally contributes to human health and well-being, especially in countries with severe weather conditions. It is generally accepted that there are six factors that determine thermal comfort conditions, namely the four environmental factors:

- air temperature (the temperature of the air measured with a thermometer in the shade),
- mean radiant temperature (corresponds to a weighted average temperature from all surfaces that surround a particular point. It is highly dependent on the materials and orientation of the building),
- relative humidity (measures the amount of moisture in the indoor air, the potential for evaporation),
- and air movement (relates to indoor air speed and direction, affects the potential for heat loss via air convection).

Together with two additional personal factors:

- clothing level (the insulating characteristics of clothing inhibit heat loss from the human body)
- and activity (muscular activity directly impacts the metabolic rate, thus heat production).

2.2.1.3 Visual comfort

Visual comfort refers to the subjective satisfaction and well-being of individuals in relation to their visual environment, particularly within indoor spaces. It involves the perception of light, lighting conditions, and the overall visual aspects of a space. There are several studies pointing out the importance of increased access to daylight and views on overall wellbeing and productivity. Optimal lighting ensures the occupant's performance and minimizes eye tiredness. The aim of this indicator is foremost to provide the means to improve and optimise lighting and visual comfort conditions, while also considering the positive influence that natural lighting can have on occupants, as referred to in the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive. The most critical factors influencing the occupant's visual comfort are presented below:

- Daylight provision: Daylight is the most desirable type of illuminance of space as it is the more relaxing to eyes than artificial lighting as well as it positively influences the mood of the occupant. This aspect can be influenced by a number of factors, such as: architectural design of the building, surrounding objects (trees, other buildings). Potential trade-offs from excessive daylighting (e.g. glare, overheating) should also be considered as well as the integration of shading devices.
- Glare: The design of the building could significantly increase or decrease a glare inside. Undesirable glare from both artificial and sunlight sources can create discomfort within the indoor environment and potentially lead to higher-than-anticipated energy consumption. Therefore, even if a building design achieves optimal daylight factor for work or living areas, it may still result in undesired glare and heat gain.
- Artificial illuminance quality: The design and specification of artificial lighting should have sufficient quality and quantity for the specific building. Additionally, the colour quality and temperature of lighting fixtures are crucial factors that could impact vision and concentration. It is the most critical parameter when it comes to visual comfort.

2.2.1.4 Indoor Air Quality

Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) refers to the air quality within and around buildings and structures, especially as it relates to the health and comfort of building occupants. Indoor pollution sources that release gases or particles into the air are the primary cause of indoor air quality problems. Inadequate ventilation can increase indoor pollutant levels by not bringing in enough outdoor air to dilute emissions from indoor sources and by not carrying air pollutants out of the building. High temperature and humidity levels can also increase concentrations of some pollutants. Inside air includes pollutants that penetrate from the outdoors, as well as sources that are unique to the indoor environment. These sources involve:

- human activities within buildings, such as smoking, burning solid fuels, cooking, and cleaning,
- vapours from building and construction materials, equipment, and furniture,
- biological contaminants, such as mould, viruses, or allergens.

The relative importance of any single source depends on how much of a given pollutant it emits and how hazardous those emissions are. In some cases, factors such as how old the source is and whether it is properly maintained are significant. For example, an improperly adjusted gas stove can emit significantly more carbon monoxide than one that is properly adjusted. Some sources, such as building materials, furnishings, and products like air fresheners, can release pollutants more or less continuously. Other sources, related to activities like smoking, cleaning, redecorating, or doing hobbies release pollutants intermittently. Unvented or malfunctioning appliances or improperly used products can release higher

and sometimes dangerous levels of pollutants indoors. Pollutant concentrations can remain in the air for extended periods after some activities.

2.3 Energy performance

Energy performance KPI in the context of energy efficiency of buildings is a quantifiable measure used to assess the overall environmental impact and efficiency of a building throughout its entire life cycle, from construction and operation to demolition or decommissioning. This KPI evaluates various stages of the building's life cycle, including materials sourcing, construction processes, energy consumption during operation, maintenance practices, and end-of-life considerations such as demolition, reuse, or recycling. It provides insights into the holistic environmental footprint of the building, including embodied energy, carbon emissions, resource depletion, and waste generation, helping stakeholders make informed decisions to minimize environmental impacts and optimize sustainability performance over the building's entire lifespan.

2.3.1 Energy efficiency

Energy efficiency⁴ indicators could be derived purely from raw data on energy consumption, measured in units like kWh or MJ, over a specific time frame. However, in most practical scenarios, it's more meaningful to define the energy indicator as a key value for energy performance, where energy consumption is normalized to a constant reference to accommodate variations in production or climatic conditions. Theoretically, an ideal energy indicator would provide consistent information about the energy performance of a process, unaffected by factors other than the actual operation. However, in reality, achieving such an ideal is improbable because most indicators are susceptible to external variables. These variables can sometimes impact the indicator to such a degree that it becomes unstable and ineffective as a management tool.

The measurement of building energy efficiency often involves quantifying it in kilowatt-hours (kWh) of the annually supplied energy, which can be assessed in numerous ways: in terms of final energy, primary energy, energy cost, or its impact on the climate. Additionally, this data can be further categorized based on energy sources, including both on-site and off-site renewables.

2.3.2 Real-time consumption

Real-time consumption encompasses the energy usage of building-related utilities like heating, ventilation, etc. but also plug loads or electric vehicle charging. The energy delivered can originate from any energy carrier, including fossil fuels, electricity, thermal energy, or biomass. Submetering can be utilized to differentiate between various applications or the origin of energy, distinguishing between renewable and non-renewable sources.

Incorporating actual measured energy consumption data into EPCs could enhance existing energy performance evaluation methods or potentially form the basis for alternative evaluation approaches, supplanting current methods. When an energy performance rating method, wherein an energy performance indicator is compared to one or more references, relies on measured energy consumption, it is referred to as operational rating.

Actual measured energy consumption data can be sourced from energy bills, meter readings, or building energy monitoring systems, offering varying levels of detail concerning time resolution, subsystem measurement locations, and monitoring parameters. Data from smart meters can be supplemented with information on building geometry and weather conditions obtained from online databases or the internet. With the increasing availability of data from smart meters and on-site measurement devices, improved accuracy becomes feasible, thereby enhancing the relevance of this KPI.

⁴ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rozwoj-technologie/efektywnosci-energetycznej-budynkow>

2.4 Financial

The financial indicators aim to increase user awareness about the energy efficiency of buildings by the approach to monetising the energy consumption, which means that the energy consumption is translated into currency. Users are able to see how much money they are spending on energy and compare it with different scenarios (asset values, operational values, prediction values). Such indicators are expected to enable the financial assessment of the building and thus provide additional information to the user. This could encourage them to adapt their behaviour in order to improve the energy efficiency of the building. Besides the comparison between the monetized energy consumptions, the financial indicator cloud also includes the expected cost for the replacement and maintenance of the building's systems and envelope. In this way, the user will be informed about the approximate expenses in the near future, which will allow him to better plan his expenditures.

2.4.1 Costs

The primary objective of the costs KPI is to offer more detailed insights into expenses by incorporating additional specialized indicators. These indicators play a crucial role in accurately assessing the condition of a building and gauging potential advantages stemming from renovation decisions. It's crucial not only to factor in energy-related expenses but also to account for other costs over the building's remaining lifespan associated with energy efficiency, health, and well-being.

2.4.2 Value

The main goal of value KPI is to inform valuations and renovation decisions by providing a protocol and better highlighting the links between building characteristics and performance and financial value input parameters and financial value. The inputs into the value KPI encompass several factors, including:

- **Cash Flow Analysis:** This involves assessing the flow of money over the calculation period, incorporating factors such as cost indicators, energy savings, operational and maintenance expenses, as well as the performance regarding health and well-being.
- **Comprehensive Risk Assessment:** This entails a detailed evaluation of risks related to marketability, vacancy rates, and occupancy levels, among others.
- **Determination of End Value:** This considers factors like the aging of the structure and its subsequent value for potential sale in the future.

2.4.3 Risks

The Risk Key Performance Indicator (KPI) aims to deliver a comprehensive risk assessment to evaluate and compare buildings. This assessment is designed to offer a simplified rating, condensing the potential impacts of energy efficiency, health, well-being, and broader aspects of understanding building characteristics. Most important risks to factor are the pathway toward Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB)⁵, focusing on financial risks and asset futureproofing. The potential risks integrated into KPIs include:

- **Energy Performance:** The energy rating provides insight into a building's compliance with future regulations to achieve NZEB targets by 2050. In the short term, monitoring energy usage and verifying performance offer a direct means to assess building operation quality and mitigate potential dysfunctions. High energy usage poses a risk to commercial viability and may necessitate future capital expenditure for renovations. The risk escalates when stricter energy regulations are imminent and there is an oversupply of energy-efficient buildings compared to demand.
- **Health and Well-being Performance:** The indoor environment significantly influences tenant attraction and retention. Failing to provide a satisfactory indoor environment increases the risk

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https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/nearly-zero-energy-and-zero-emission-buildings_en

regarding commercialization and occupancy rates. This risk intensifies when there's an oversupply of buildings with good indoor quality relative to demand.

- **Cost Management:** Effective cost management enables owners to identify discrepancies and malfunctions, enhancing building management. Inadequate cost capture and management elevate operational risks.
- **Information Management:** Proper data capture and management are pivotal in real estate management, with increasing emphasis placed on data integrity. A failure to present organized and exploitable data regarding building characteristics and performance heightens the risk. Prospective owners may presume worst-case scenarios to fill information gaps, potentially incurring additional expenses for data collection.

Furthermore, there are risks associated with sustainability-related information, including environmental hazards, climate change adaptation, and functional obsolescence stemming from evolving lifestyles and work patterns.

2.5 Climate change

Climate change is defined as the impact of human emissions on the radiative forcing (i.e. heat radiation absorption) of the atmosphere. This may, in turn, have adverse impacts on ecosystem health, human health, and material welfare. Most of these emissions enhance radiative forcing, causing the temperature at the earth's surface to rise, i.e. the greenhouse effect. The areas of protection are human health, the natural environment, and the man-made environment.

This KPI typically quantifies the reduction in greenhouse gas emissions resulting from energy-saving measures implemented within buildings, such as insulation upgrades, the use of energy-efficient appliances, and the adoption of renewable energy sources. It serves as a tool for evaluating progress towards sustainability goals, guiding decision-making processes, and identifying areas for further improvement in building design, construction, and operation to minimize environmental impact and enhance resilience to climate change effects.

2.5.1 Impact

The Impact on Climate Change KPI in the context of energy efficiency of buildings represents a quantifiable measure of the direct influence buildings have on mitigating or exacerbating climate change through their energy usage and efficiency practices. Those KPIs can explore such things as the influence of buildings on urban heat island degree-hours, which compare the outdoor temperature in rural and urban areas. Furthermore, they could provide data about the shading of other buildings and green spaces as well as the surfaces with high solar reflection values.

There is also a potential in the use of Life Cycle Assessment⁶. LCA enables the assessment of the environmental impact of any system throughout its life cycle by considering the required input and associated output resources of that system. Examples of LCA Indicators include "Energy savings", expressed in "Embodied energy/m²" and "Carbon reductions", expressed in "Carbon dioxide equivalent/m²".

2.5.2 Sustainability

Level(s)⁷ serve as the standardized framework within the European Union for fundamental sustainability indicators in building construction, therefore sustainability KPIs are based on this framework. The primary objective of Level(s) is to empower professionals engaged in building projects to actively contribute to broader environmental enhancements at the European level. It aims to establish a shared vocabulary of sustainability by delineating essential indicators for evaluating the sustainability of buildings. Based on six macro-objectives, the Level(s) framework outlines strategic priorities for buildings:

⁶ ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework

⁷ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels_en

- greenhouse gas emissions along a building life cycle,
- resource efficient and circular material life cycles,
- efficient use of water resources,
- adaption and resilience to climate change,
- optimised life cycle cost and value.

Furthermore, Level(s) assists building professionals in enhancing the sustainability of existing building stock by futureproofing against climate change through renovation efforts. It enables consideration of the entire carbon impact, encompassing both embodied and operational emissions when planning renovations. Balancing clients' immediate requirements with the flexibility to adapt properties as needs evolve is crucial for extending building lifespans, and Level(s) facilitate this consideration within the design process.

Figure 1 Tree diagram of identified KPIs

3 Analysis of KPIs and new scales in other Horizon 2020 projects

3.1 ALDREN

ALDREN – ALliance for Deep RENovation in Buildings ⁸– is a European project funded by the European Union in the scope of the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program. ALDREN targets and supports investments in deep renovation, encouraging key Building stakeholders to contribute to the “Renovation wave” that has been announced in the European Green Deal. To be efficient, the Green Deal will have to be consistent from the political top level to the identification of relevant renovation actions by owners and consultants, investment decisions from the financial sector and application on the field by qualified building professionals. ALDREN proposes a transparent, consistent, common EU wide assessment framework to trigger more ambitious renovation projects through the inclusion of improved sustainability metrics in certifications and the use of decision-support protocols and tools.

Table 2 KPIs in ALDREN project

<p>Energy rating and target – European Voluntary certificate (EVC) –The EVC improves the current practice at least by the following features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• local climate is used for the energy performance calculation instead of one national or regional climate. The gap between calculated and actual energy consumption is reduced,• common harmonised calculation methodology based on CEN EPB standards that improves comparability of energy performance across the EU,• The hourly calculation step provides a more correct consideration of thermal comfort and correct estimation of some technologies e.g. PV auto-consumption, heat pumps,• thermal comfort score from the hourly calculation is reported together with the energy use to make visible the relation between the calculated energy use and the IEQ,• additional indicators are reported (health & wellbeing, measured energy, financial valuation) – recommendations for improvement of energy performance towards the NZEB are reported with link to the details in the Renovation Roadmap to avoid the lock-in effect.
<p>Energy verification – ALDREN NZEB is defined by energy class “A” and by three additional requirements specified in the protocol. The numerical value for ALDREN NZEB may not necessarily be in the compliance with the national definition of NZEB due to the diverse types of indicators, the different assessment boundaries and the calculation methodologies used at national level.</p>
<p>Comfort & well-being – The index proposed by ALDREN is called TAIL, T standing for thermal environment, A for acoustic environment, I for indoor air quality and L for light (visual environment). TAIL integrates thus the four central components describing indoor environmental quality. The overall principle of TAIL is that it presents the quality of each of the components defining indoor environmental quality separately and then integrates them into one index describing the overall quality of indoor environment, all shown as one label or a tag.</p>
<p>Cost, value, and risk – ALDREN has developed a methodology for financial valuation of renovation action, which focuses on the provision of relevant ALDREN sustainability metrics (energy, IEQ) and detailed technical and performance information about renovation actions to financial analysts. ALDREN specifies indicators and information to be shared alongside the most relevant financial information for building valuation (such as the building’s lease structure or local market data, including rental values, rental growth rates or duration to let).</p>

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/754159>

3.2 D²EPC

D²EPC⁹ aims to set the grounds for the next generation of dynamic Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) for buildings. The proposed framework sets its foundations on the smart-readiness level of the buildings and the corresponding data collection infrastructure and management systems. It is fed by operational data and adopts the 'digital twin' concept to advance Building Information Modelling, calculate a novel set of energy, environmental, financial and human comfort/ wellbeing indicators, and through them the EPC classification of the building in question.

Table 3 KPIs in D²EPC project

<p>SRI - In establishing the SRI methodology, three technical studies prepared by Vito, upon the request of the European Union, were consulted. These studies developed an assessment scheme for a separate, brief and detailed classification of the smartness rate of buildings. The rating scheme assesses 9 domains as follows: 1. Heating 2. Cooling 3. Domestic hot water 4. Ventilation 5. Lighting 6. Dynamic building envelope 7. Electricity 8. Electric vehicle charging 9. Monitoring and control</p>
<p>Human-Centric (IEQ, thermal, visual, acoustic comfort) - Within D²EPC, the occupant's comfort and wellbeing are examined in the context of three different indoor environmental quality pillars, i.e., the thermal and visual comfort as well as the quality of indoor air. To quantify the building's overall comfort performance, various environmental parameters are utilised, along with the respective boundaries of proper building operation per parameter. The approach steps on the personalised comfort profiling engine which contains a machine-learning clustering algorithm able to identify patterns and trends on preceding user data to infer the occupant's preferred limits. After the boundary determination, the KPIs are calculated based on methodologies recommended by European and national standards to evaluate the building's performance in a clearly defined manner.</p>
<p>Energy performance Indicators (Power, Heating, DHW, Cooling, Lighting, Appliances) - D²EPC includes a set of indicators which is related to the environmental and energy performance of buildings. The importance of employing LCA methodologies for the efficient energy design of buildings and for enabling the parameterization of its embodied energy and primary energy demand are highlighted for their inclusion in the dynamic EPCs, mainly addressed to relevant stakeholders, as well as to practising engineers and EPC assessors, anticipating to implement the principles of D²EPC in buildings certification. It is proposed that the energy and environmental D²EPC indicators, which illustrate building sustainability impact, be included in the next-generation EPCs.</p>
<p>Financial - The development of financial indicators is based on the well-established concept of whole life cycle costing (LCC). The LCC methodology is a decision-making tool that helps assess different options over a certain period. The indicators, developed in D²EPC are not intended for the long-term planning or comparison of alternatives; nevertheless, the LCC concept is used as a base, as it defines a typical scope of costs throughout the construction, operation, maintenance, and end-of-life phase. Therefore, the approach is to evaluate the relevant costs and present them to the user as additional information in next-generation dynamic EPCs. The included financial indicators are: As-operated costs, As-designed costs, Total cost comparison (graphically presented), Predicted costs, and Expected costs for building systems.</p>

3.3 E-DYCE

E-DYCE (Energy flexible DYnamic building CErtification)¹⁰ is the natural evolution of the conventional Energy Performance Certification into real time optimization of building performance and comfort, by capturing the building's dynamic behaviour, and at the same time providing transparent feedback, through an intuitive interface. E-DYCE will drastically increase the reliability of the energy performance assessment process. It will support communication between labelling professionals and building owners, to cultivate benefits in both indoor climate and energy savings. It is complimentary to the current EPC

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/892984>

¹⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/893945>

labelling method and not competitive, bringing and standing for all the value of the next generation of certification and building energy assessment. In the current generation of steady-state EPCs, the free-running potential of buildings is not considered, neither are included in the labelling stock buildings without heating installed or those of old cultural heritage. On the opposite side, smartness in buildings easy to cope with changes, are not rewarded when buildings are labelled. Overheating, low comfort, demotivation for renovations can be named, as results of poor decisions taken through EPCs.

The transition to dynamic calculations must be supported by optimized and structured processes: efficient input data acquisition, data storage, interoperability, and transparent presentation and communication with the user.

E-DYCE aligned with current Energy Performance Building Directive (EPBD) and near Zero Energy Building (nZEB) definitions, can be applied to any building of any typology, location or smartness level and will generate substantial savings of one energy class by guiding the user to unlock the potential of free running operation.

Table 4 KPIs in E-DYCE project

Energy and energy efficiency (including a reduction in energy needs) - From a general point of view, the building energy performance gap is linked to several issues and causes:

- The adoption of simplified simulation approaches (like steady-state ones).
- Potential errors (model operators) in model data inputting.
- The use of common and standardized data in simulation (e.g., the building U-value, the airtight and air exchange).
- The adoption of standard climate conditions.
- The adoption of user standard profiles and behaviours.
- The adoption of standard set-points or the definition of inaccurate expected indoor temperatures.
- The interaction between occupants and technologies.

Operational management and occupant/technology interactions, underline the importance of supporting communications with users to obtain large reductions in EPG thanks to an enhancement of their ability in energy-saving. User information is hence an essential aspect to be considered in reducing EPG during operational phases and this is a topic that is faced within E-DYCE. Additionally, it is also possible to classify performance-gap causes according to different building phases, assuming 3 classes

- Design-phase correlated causes.
- Construction-phase correlated causes.
- And operational phase correlated causes.

This classification underlines performance-gap causes that base in the design choices and in the correct interpretation of design impacts on energy needs, on construction issues, e.g., insulation gaps, bad positioning/installation of services or components, and on operational causes correlated to an optimisation of energy service management, user activation, and behaviours. The last, may also be connected to unexpected changes in building fabric behaviours (e.g., internal temperature variations during unheated periods). From a general point of view at least 3 types of building performance gaps exist:

- Regulatory performance gap.
- Static performance gap.
- Dynamic performance gap.

Where, the regulatory PG (performance gap) refers to the discrepancies between results from compliance energy modelling tools and measured energy consumptions, the static PG compares performance simulation predictions (potentially including unregulated loads) and measured data, and the dynamic performance gap analyses differences between calibrated dynamic energy models and actual energy consumptions.

Free running operation and potential exploitation (including temperature performances) - To evaluate a building that works in free-running conditions and/or to evaluate the free-running potential in design rating, it was demonstrated that an additional issue needs to be considered: the comfort/discomfort levels. As it mentioned above, in free-running conditions mechanical equipment (e.g., heating/cooling) is absent or turned off. For this reason, it is not present a direct energy consumption/need for guaranteeing the set indoor comfort thresholds (e.g., heating set point temperature or cooling set point temperature). Hence, the main issue is the ability of the building and building components to reach and maintain space comfort conditions by interacting with the environment in free-running mode. In energy evaluations of building performances, the energy efficiency is reached by reducing the amount of energy needs to maintain the set acceptable comfort levels, while in free running spaces the main topic becomes the deterioration of comfort thresholds. For this reason, additional key performance indicators (KPIs) and methodologies are needed to define and evaluate comfort levels. Furthermore, this issue introduces an additional challenge correlated to the adoption of proper comfort models, considering the differences in people perception and acceptability threshold in mechanically and naturally heated/cooled spaces.

Energy demand forecast - Predicting the energy performance of a building can be done based on white-, grey- and black-box models, with varying degrees of mechanistic complexities. White-box models are physics-based approaches in which detailed physical information about the building operation with a high level of accuracy is required. Black-box models are statistical data-driven approaches, in which, despite the automatic adjustment of parameters and rapid automated identification of outputs principles of physics are big disadvantages compared to the white-box approaches. In fact, being data-driven, black-box models can be inconsistent with physical reality where little building system data is available. Like white-box models, black-box models can have static or dynamic, linear or nonlinear internal structures. Grey-box models are a hybrid of white-box and black-box models. Grey-box parameters are, fully or partly, determined based on measured data of the real system. Grey-box models can be useful where the detailed thermal mass characteristics of building are missing and where the occupants' behaviours are uncertain.

Comfort/quality (including thermal comfort improvement, indoor air quality) - One of the most relevant issues for building occupants is to get the right temperature in their living spaces. Nevertheless, thermal comfort is directly related to different domains: thermal physiology (heat production and usage in humans), physics (heat transfer from body skin to the environment), sociology (reactions to the environment), and building fields (space design to better guarantee thermal user requirements). Clearly thermal perception is a subjective issue, nevertheless general indices may be derived according to statistical considerations. One of the scales commonly used is the one adopted by ASHRAE Standard 55 that bases on a 7-step domain from -3 (cold) to +3 (hot) passing through neutral conditions. In case in which natural ventilation and building design choices (e.g., bioclimatic issues) are not able to guarantee the defined comfort category, this needs to be mentioned in building design documents, and for E-DYCE to be referred to the proposed dynamic label. The adaptive model is based on regressed operative temperature plotted as function of the external running mean temperature. This approach is applied to summer and shoulder seasons (neutral spring and autumn periods), while for winter, the same temperature control limits of mechanically cooled buildings are applied. The running mean temperature is a function of the daily running mean outdoor temperature.

Smartness readiness - SRI will be considered in E-DYCE KPIs definition. In particular, E-DYCE enables the 3 key functionalities in line with EPBD 2018 and the mentioned Commission Delegated Regulations (Annex I): - energy performance and operation; - response to the needs of the occupants; and - energy flexibility, including the ability of the building or building unit to enable participation in demand response. Furthermore, the seven impact criteria [energy efficiency, maintenance and fault prediction, comfort, convenience, health/well-being and accessibility, information to occupants, energy flexibility and storage] and their univocal correlation with a key functionality are assumed. Finally, the nine technological domains [heating, cooling, DHW, ventilation, lighting, dynamic building envelope, electricity, electric vehicle charging, and monitoring and control] are also assumed.

Economic indices - Several economic KPIs are connected to building energy and environmental performances, and/or are correlated to the NZEB and EPC definition. It is possible to mention the adoption of Global Cost indicator for which a sequential search-optimization technique was developed. This indicator takes into account the global cost referred to the starting year, the initial investment cost, is the annual cost during year of component including the annual running costs (energy costs, operational costs, maintenance costs) and periodic replacement costs.

Climate change impact indices – Several indicators can assess the correlation between buildings, their surroundings and climate, such as: Urban heat island degree-hours (UHIdh) and urban cool island degree-hours (UCIdh) which compare the outdoor temperature in rural and urban areas; the impact of building on the external spaces; carbon emissions based on the electricity and natural gas consumptions in a building; carbon intensity of an asset based on final energy consumption; usage of renewable energy sources that contribute in GHG savings.

3.4 EFFECT4buildings

The project EFFECT4buildings¹¹ develops in collaboration with public building managers a comprehensive decision-making support toolbox with a set of financial instruments to unlock the investments and lower the risks of implementing energy efficiency measures (retrofitting, upgrading and deep renovation) in buildings owned by public stakeholders.

Tools can be divided into two categories: financial instruments and supportive tools. Financial instruments are more complex tools which help to finance or optimize investments in energy efficiency projects. Supportive tools help to achieve the goal of the energy efficiency projects. They can be used as a part of financial instrument or separately. For all tools and instruments, actual technical solutions are central parts of the toolbox.

Table 5 KPIs in EFFECT4buildings project

Financial - EFFECT4buildings have developed two financial calculation tools to evaluate diverse options in a decision-making process in energy efficiency investments. Planning a new energy efficiency investment benefit from estimating its life cycle costs. It can be done using cash flow analysis, by predicting all costs and benefits during the investment's life cycle. For the investments with long life cycle, it is beneficial to use discounted cash flows, which called Net present value (NPV). Alternative economic method is Internal rate of return (IRR). The internal rate of return is the discount rate, which makes investments net present value to 0. IRR is a very useful method for decision makers to estimate the profitability of the investment. These methods are particularly suitable for choosing different kinds of technical solutions for energy efficiency in buildings that may have different initial investment costs, different operating, maintenance and repair costs, and possibly different technical lifetime. Complementary calculation methods should also be implemented as a standard for energy serving companies, for example, in energy audits. To help estimate and understand the profitability of an energy efficiency investment, the tool uses the following methods to compare alternative energy efficiency measures:

Cash flow,

Net present value,

Internal rate of return,

Pay-back time,

Carbon dioxide emissions.

The tool also includes sensitivity analysis, with options to estimate energy and water price changes. In doing so, the tool helps analyse and compare possible future development paths. The calculations can also take into account non-energy benefits.

3.5 Epanacea

The objective of the ePANACEA¹² project is to develop a holistic methodology for energy performance assessment and certification of buildings that can overcome the challenges (lack of accuracy, a gap

¹¹ <https://www.effect4buildings.se/>

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/892421>

between theoretical and real consumption patterns, absence of proper protocols for inclusion of smart and novel technologies, little convergence across EU schemes, lack of trust in the market and very little user awareness related to energy efficiency). The vision is that ePANACEA becoming a relevant instrument in the European energy transition through the building sector.

ePANACEA comprises the creation of a prototype (the Smart Energy Performance Assessment Platform) making use of the most advanced techniques in dynamic and automated simulation modelling, big data analysis and machine learning, inverse modelling or the estimation of potential energy savings and economic viability check.

Table 6 KPIs in the Epanacea project

<p>SRI - A successful implementation of the SRI scheme relies on its capacity to bring additional value to the building assessment. While evidence tends to demonstrate that the EPC assessment is an effective mechanism to determine the theoretical energy performance of the building and to propose certain renovation recommendations, it also presents certain gaps and inaccuracies. The EPC barely considers the assessment of comfort and wellbeing and completely lacks the consideration of data technologies such as fault detection, grid connectivity or storage. Based on the input provided by the ePANACEA experts it is explored how a potential synergy between the EPC and the SRI could generate new market value assessed in terms of their impact on the national economy, impact on the building users' trust, impact on renovation rate and building energy efficiency, methodological benefits.</p> <p>A good degree of complementarity exists between EPC and SRI schemes. Beyond the addition of valuable content, the information required to assess the SRI can be used to improve the quality and reliability of current EPC schemes. The EPC and SRI schemes are complementary rather than overlapping and thus a combined approach which integrates both within one assessment has limited impact on cost reduction, as could be expected.</p>
<p>Real data consumption - EU legislation is fostering the implementation (or usage) of smart meters and IoT devices which allow monitoring of various energy flows and building occupancy. The information derived from the smart meters and IoT devices enables development of new services and approaches for building performance assessments. Methods using measured data with limited post-processing can serve as an informative aspect additional to the theoretical assessment. This project has explored various data sources that can supplement an energy performance certificate (EPC) and related aspects which can influence the feasibility of including such data in EPC assessments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inventory of data variables. The nature of data available on individual building energy use. The accessibility of the data for the use within EPC schemes, including an exploration of (energy) databases availability. Identification (measurement) and post-processing methods.

3.6 EPC RECAST

The EPC RECAST¹³ project will develop a well-structured process and a toolbox that will support the development, performance and validation of new EPCs with a particular focus on existing residential buildings with high retrofit needs.

EPC RECAST is developing a transparent, common and explicit data model (i.e. input data to be collected for EPC assessments and calculations) which will support the characterization of existing buildings and dwellings during on-site inspections by professional certifiers and improve the comparability between EPCs.

¹³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/893118>

By involving end-users in multiple steps throughout the design phase of the next generation EPCs, the project aims to provide more user-friendly EPCs. The aim is for these EPCs to provide an easier understanding of the energy performance results and context-specific renovation roadmaps.

EPC RECAST will also provide operational and detailed guidelines about the developed tools and methodologies to facilitate the on-site collection of relevant data and parameters by assessors.

Providing an improved calibration of building energy modelling through the cross-exploitation of measured energy-related data and energy performance calculation tool.

Table 7 KPIs in EPC RECAST project.

IEQ – No publicly available data.
Wellbeing (health-related, comfort) – No publicly available data.
Smartness (SRI) – No publicly available data.
Investments – No publicly available data.
CO₂ indicator – No publicly available data.

The approach will rely on both building intrinsic performances and output-based assessments exploiting available building energy related data, will connect with smart-readiness assessment, and will go beyond energy to include CO₂ reduction, comfort, indoor air quality, and health-related indicators.

EPC RECAST has developed a monitoring strategy that has been based on different building and systems typologies, representative of the actual residential EU housing stock, by introducing the concept of “levels of monitoring”. Three main levels have been set: Basic Level–BL; Medium Level–ML; and Advanced Level–AL. The identified levels have been used for categorizing the buildings and defining the most suitable low-cost, low-impact monitoring approach for gathering the energy consumption data. The three levels identify different energy generation concept (centralized or independent) and the presence of different utility meter typology (electromechanical or smart energy meter).

3.7 EUB SuperHub

EUB SuperHub¹⁴ project will support the creation of a harmonized certification process in the EU by developing a scalable methodology to view, assess and monitor the buildings throughout their life cycle.

EUB SuperHub wants the EPC to reach its market disruptive potential by leveraging on the powers of the 4.0 era and the digital twin technology to transform the process of storing, maintaining and communicating the EPC. The EUB SuperHub certification scheme and tools are designed to enable the creation of demand-driven market by addressing the needs of multiple stakeholders groups with an online hub (one-stop shop) platform that uses a harmonized criterion.

The harmonized criteria will enable holistic assessments of buildings and districts on the basis of the EU EVCS, Level(s) and SRI indicators. The EUB SuperHub platform and framework goal is to tie the „distributed” systems, assessment schemes and market actors under a common hub (one-stop shop).

Table 8 KPIs in the EUB SuperHub project

SRI indicators – No publicly available data.

¹⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101033916>

3.8 iBRoad2EPC

The iBRoad2EPC¹⁵ project represents the next step in energy performance assessment schemes and certification practices, promoting and showcasing the integration of Building Renovation Passport elements into EPC schemes. Building on the results of the iBRoad project (2017-2020) which developed, tested and delivered a model for the Building Renovation Passport supporting single-family homeowners with personalized advice to facilitate stepwise deep renovation, iBRoad2EPC aims to bridge the Building Renovation Passport with the EPC, and expand, improve and broaden their format and joint scope to consider additional features and become applicable also to multi-family and public buildings. The aim is to improve reliability, usefulness and effectiveness, thereby establishing the next generation of EPCs that will support Europe's decarbonization ambitions while improving conditions for building occupants.

The iBRoad2EPC is created with an online tool called iBRoad2EPC Assistant. The iBRoad2EPC Assistant is a backend tool that compiles and transmits data for a specific building on request. The request can be submitted from different platforms or frontends. This allows the iBRoad2EPC Assistant to be connected to various existing tools in the Member States, such as EPC software or energy performance registers. In addition, a standardized frontend for the Assistant is delivered to enable data entry independently from external software.

iBRoad2EPC follows a semi-flexible approach, in which a unified Basic Module can be complemented flexibly with additional modules. The iBRoad2EPC Basic Module comprises all core features of iBRoad2EPC. It is the indispensable basis for the implementation of iBRoad2EPC. All other modules depend on the Basic Module, as it provides the basic structure for the processing, such as the online tool for editing and creating the iBRoad2EPC as well as the basic output format. The main objective of the Basic Module is to provide the indispensable technical information for building owners that have to be included in every iBRoad2EPC.

Table 9 KPIs in the iBRoad2EPC project

Cost Module - The Investment Cost Module allows for the display of renovation costs in iBRoad2EPC. The following cost types can be presented:

- Total investment costs - The total cost of all renovation measures included in a renovation step. This is the sum that the building owners will have to pay for this step.
- Maintenance costs - Part of the total costs that has to be spent anyway for the maintenance of the building. They would arise in renovations without any energy improvement.
- Energy-related additional costs - Part of the total cost that arises only from the energy improvement.
- Funding - The presentation of the funding mainly refers to grant subsidies. They can easily be shown for each renovation step. The benefits of subsidised loans, on the other hand, can hardly be assigned to a single point in time. Therefore, loans should preferably be described in writing. A corresponding input field for free text is provided. Here, issuers can also provide links to further information.

Energy Demand Module - The Energy Demand Module adds the following information for each renovation step to the iBRoad2EPC: energy consumption, efficiency class and greenhouse gas emissions, energy costs.

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) Module - The IEQ Module allows issuers to evaluate the indoor environmental quality of a building. The IEQ comfort indicator was developed in the X-tendo project together with an assessment approach for the calculation of comfort rating covering all aspects of IEQ. iBRoad2EPC integrates this approach. For iBRoad2EPC, the CARP (Comfort Asset Rating Procedure) method is recommended. CARP is designed for new, renovated, and existing buildings that are not occupied. For the assessment of the indoor environment, the required information can be captured

¹⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101033781>

through checklists. The main determinants of IEQ are: indoor air quality, thermal comfort, lighting and acoustics.

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) Module - The concept of the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) was introduced by the European Commission. The SRI rates the readiness of buildings in performing three key functionalities: to optimise energy efficiency and overall in-use performance, to adapt their operation to the needs of the occupant and to adapt to signals from the grid (for example, energy flexibility). The SRI comprises heating, cooling, domestic hot water, ventilation, dynamic building envelope, electricity, electric vehicle charging and monitoring and control. Up to 15 subgroups can be processed for each of these services. In iBRoad2EPC, the official calculation methods and tools of the commission are used. This ensures that they are in line with the standards.

3.9 NEEM Hub

The aim of the Nordic Energy Efficient Mortgages (NEEM) Hub¹⁶ is to scale up lending to energy renovations in the Nordics to meet the EU green deal, as well as ambitious national climate targets.

The hub is comprised of a long list of institutions from the financial sector, behavioural scientists, mortgage specialists and authorities, and digital technology communities from across the Nordics, all guided by Copenhagen Economics.

The NEEM Hub adopts a bank-centric approach in breaking down the identified barriers to develop a concrete, core solution ready for implementation in the banking sector throughout the Nordics. Nordea, Swedbank, and the green fintech start-up, Hemma, have acted as market demonstrators, testing the developed solutions with a coherent value chain to enable a smooth customer journey.

Table 10 KPIs in the NEEM Hub project

Economic - The ultimate purpose of the solution is to identify, reach out to, and incentivise households where energy renovations would be beneficial, not only from a climate perspective but also from a financial perspective, where the savings in energy bills would surpass the costs entailed in such a renovation.

Real energy consumption - Energy consumption is assessed by developing a model that correlates with weather conditions. The model aims to detect indications of poor insulation or insufficient wind tightness by analyzing the impact of external temperature and wind on energy consumption. Upon estimating a household's energy efficiency, relevant renovation needs are assessed using Copenhagen Economics' renovation costs model. This model relies on correlations between enhanced energy efficiency and renovation expenses extracted from 130,000 EPC label reports. Utilizing these correlations enables the estimation of probable energy renovation costs for a specific household, as well as the identification of renovations likely to yield the greatest net savings.

3.10 PHOENIX

The PHOENIX¹⁷ is a collaborative project improving the cyber security of the European electrical power energy systems (EPES), i.e. the so-called Smart Grid. PHOENIX aims to offer a cyber-shield armour to European EPES infrastructure enabling cooperative detection of large-scale, cyber-human security and privacy incidents and attacks, guarantee the continuity of operations and minimize cascading effects in the infrastructure itself, the environment, the citizens and the end-users at a reasonable cost.

Table 11 KPIs in the PHOENIX project

SRI - No publicly available data.

¹⁶ <https://neemhub.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://phoenix-h2020.eu/>

3.11 QualDeEPC

QualDeEPC¹⁸ aims to enhance the quality and cross-EU convergence of Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) schemes, and the link between EPCs and deep renovation.

QualDeEPC will work on EU-wide convergence of the building assessment and the issuance, design, and use of quality-enhanced EPCs as well as their recommendations for building renovation. The aim is to make these recommendations coherent with deep energy renovation towards a nearly-zero energy building stock by 2050. Under the coordination of the Wuppertal Institute, the project partners will work to create consensus in the participating countries and beyond, and to implement as many improvements as possible during the project period, involving certification bodies, energy agencies, building sector and certification stakeholders, and other relevant organizations.

Table 12 KPIs in QualDeEPC project

<p>Improved classification(s), using the same scale as for the current energy class, and improved energy performance value(s) after implementing a recommended combination of renovation actions ('main option') - Most EPC issuers utilize software to assess a building's energy usage, which determines its energy class, with renovation recommendations integrated into this process to yield a new energy performance value and corresponding class. The set of renovation recommendations should be kept within a cost-effective frame, according to the EPBD. For current and future building owners and financial advisors, the display of a possibly higher energy class is highly beneficial, since it shows the potential of the building when renovated. Also, the national policymakers could use the information to check if energy saving goals can realistically be reached.</p>
<p>Potential energy savings (in kWh/yr) after implementing the 'main option' - The difference between the original and improved value can be translated into energy saving in kWh/year using the provided area of the building. Since this energy-saving value is an estimation, which also depends on the number and user profile of the building's occupants, a remark on this issue should be added as a footnote or similar. The display of possible energy savings is especially important for current and future building owners and financial advisors. National policymakers could gain a more realistic view of the energy-saving potential of the building stock.</p>
<p>Details on building envelope and building HVAC system, illustrated by a traffic light system - Most EPCs lack detailed information on building envelopes and HVAC systems, crucial for assessing existing buildings' strengths and weaknesses. Drawing from initiatives like the "dena Gütesiegel" project in Germany and Hungary's EPC renewal process, a systematic approach rates components from "bad" to "good," aiding building valuation and investment decisions. While crucial for building owners and financial advisors, this evaluation may pose a challenge for less qualified EPC issuers and compete with detailed energy audits, potentially impacting national policymakers' understanding of building stocks.</p>
<p>Detailed renovation recommendations by component, consistent with deep energy renovation, illustrated by the same traffic light system - Efforts are underway to enhance this element of the EPC forms, considering specific values for target components and estimating cost categories, albeit with acknowledged difficulty. This enhancement aims to furnish building owners and financial advisors with detailed renovation options and cost estimations, with the workload for EPC issuers varying depending on the availability of building details and the establishment of specific target values.</p>
<p>Useful combination of renovations and stepwise implementation - indicating possibilities for staged deep renovation - The current EPC forms lack a designated space for detailing useful renovation combinations and their stepwise implementation, hindering the development of individual building renovation roadmaps. Recognizing the importance of this information for building owners and financial advisors, it is necessary to integrate an empty field for such details, which can also serve as a foundation for energy consultants conducting audits.</p>

¹⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/847100>

3.12 SmartLivingEPC

SmartLivingEPC¹⁹ project aims to deliver a certificate which will be issued with the use of digitized tools and retrieve the necessary assessment information for the building shell and building systems from BIM literacy, including enriched energy and sustainability-related information for the as designed and the actual performance of the building. The new certification scheme will also expand its scope, covering aspects related to water consumption, as well as noise pollution and acoustics. SmartLivingEPC certificate will be fully compatible with digital logbooks, as well as with building renovation passports in order to allow the integration of the building energy performance information in digital databases. A special aspect of SmartLivingEPC will be its application in building complexes, with the aim of energy certification at the neighbourhood scale.

Table 13 KPIs in the SmartLivingEPC project

<p>SRI - The final report of the second SRI technical study investigated three potential SRI assessment methods (i.e., Method A, Method B, and Method C). Methods A and B are based on the assessment of the smart-ready services that are present or planned at the design stage and their functionality level. The assessment aims to determine with sufficient reliability what services are present or planned, and if so, the functionality level for each of those services. The main difference is that Method A considers a reduced service catalogue and thus spans a subset of the smart-ready services considered in Method B. Consequently, Method A requires less effort, time, and potential expertise. By default, Method B would require an on-site inspection of the assessed object. Alternatively, Method C aims to be based on measured data, quantifying the operational smartness of in-use buildings. Methods A and B are methodologies included in the SRI assessment package produced by the SRI support team, whereas Method C is considered a potential future evolution. The project embraces the SRI assessment procedure taken as reference Method B and the default calculation methodology.</p>
<p>Level(s) - Operational IEQ assessment indicators are measurable indicators specified in the Level(s) framework. Level(s) is an assessment and reporting framework that provides a common language for sustainability performance of buildings. Level(s) promotes lifecycle thinking for buildings and provides a robust approach to measuring and supporting improvement from design to end of life, for both residential buildings and offices. IEQ indicators can be found in "Health and comfort" area from 4.1 to 4.4.</p>
<p>Energy performance rating - The operational or measured energy indicator is a performance indicator that assesses the energy performance of a building based on actual energy consumption or usage data. It is a ratio that compares the amount of energy used or consumed by a building to its size, occupancy, or other relevant factors. This indicator is commonly used to evaluate the energy efficiency of buildings, identify areas of improvement, and measure the effectiveness of energy management strategies</p>
<p>Results from HVAC audits - Integration of information derived from energy performance inspections/audits of HVAC systems into the SmartLivingEPC asset rating's calculation methodology, both at the building and complex level. In broad terms, the methodology entails:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Conducting an analysis of the inputs and findings (outputs) of the technical inspection audits for building systems.• Identifying and listing the main findings from the technical inspection audits which can be used for the energy classification.• Developing the necessary procedures and methodology, to enable the utilization of the findings of building systems periodic audits in the process of calculating the asset energy class of buildings.

¹⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069639>

3.13 TIMEPAC

TIMEPAC²⁰ aims to help improve existing energy certification processes and move from single, static certification to more holistic and dynamic approaches. At five demonstration sites, TIMEPAC is developing new methods and tools to provide an improved basis for data collection and analysis. As a result, Energy Performance Certificates will be enriched with concrete retrofitting solutions and experts can be better trained to make our homes fit for the future.

TIMEPAC will improve the existing certification process across countries through Transversal Deployment Scenarios. Each TDS encompasses various stages of the EPC workflow (generation, storage, analysis, and exploitation), involving multiple stakeholders (research groups, energy agencies, ESCOS, etc.) and resources (data, tools, methods).

Table 14 KPIs in the TIMEPAC project

SRI - In the framework of the TIMEPAC project, two assessment methods are employed: a simplified assessment method and a detailed assessment method. The simplified method (Method A) uses a reduced set of services, which requires less effort and expertise to conduct the assessment. In the final stage of TDS4, the detailed method (Method B) will be used to compare the smart readiness of similar building types. In this process a use-case approach that focuses on the following end-users will be used:

- Demand-Side-Management-aware facility manager,
- Cost-conscious facility manager,
- Sustainability-supporting owner,
- Informed tenant,
- Informed ESCO,
- Informed utility.

A use-case approach is a methodology used to capture the potential benefits of a tested tool from the end-users perspective. The end-users are the group of potential users or beneficiaries of the SRI. In this phase, assessors will need to act as end-users and perform the SRI calculation, while keeping in mind the main needs of adopted end-user's role. All the comments that are entered into the SRI calculation spreadsheet will be used to extract potential energy efficiency and flexibility measures.

Environmental sustainability indicators - The basic idea is that the levels represent a professional journey from the initial concept through design, construction and then, after handover, to the reality of the completed building. Progression through the levels also represents an increase in the accuracy and reliability of the reporting - the higher the level, the closer the reported results will be to providing data that reflects the performance of the building as-built and in use.

The approach first step for the TIMEPAC partners in their respective countries is to establish a TIMEPAC TDS 4 calculation plan:

- TDS 4 will address certain indicators under macro-objectives:
 - 1 (Greenhouse gas and air pollutants for a building's lifecycle),
 - 4 (Healthy and comfortable spaces),
 - 6 (Optimised lifecycle cost and value).
- In order to assess performance, the indicators used are:
 - Use-stage energy performance (mandatory),
 - Lifecycle Global Warming Potential (voluntary),
 - Time outside of thermal comfort range (mandatory),
 - Lifecycle costs (mandatory).
- Partner(s) in their respective countries have to establish to which 'level' the project performance will be assessed.

²⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101033819>

- Partner(s) in their respective countries have to plan which resources will be needed to assess performance and when in the project's lifecycle.

3.14 TripleA-reno

The vision of the TripleA-Reno²¹ project is to promote widespread energy renovation of existing European housing stock and empower individuals and communities in favour of such developments. The ultimate goal of the project is to provide tools to simplify the renovation efforts for designers and practitioners, expedite the renovation process as a whole, and ensure high quality results for the end users. TripleA-reno project achieves this aim by developing an open end-user centred gamified platform that:

- fosters new consumer and end-user centred business models and decision support tools, using evidence-based performances that facilitate decision-making,
- improves performances of deep renovation by enhanced quality control, supported by targeted CPD and training,
- provides consumers and end-users of deep renovation projects with attractive, understandable and personalized information of realised real performance,
- demonstrate the benefits and evidence-based solutions in live demonstration cases,
- rolls out the results on a wider European scale by in TripleA-Reno involved European interest groups and umbrella associations.

Table 15 KPIs in TripleA-Reno project

Energy performance - This concept relates to the 'Enhance transparency' recommendation from D2.6 about users' feedback and response to the activities performed with them and at their homes, which among others, suggests to provide traceability and recognition of all actors/stakeholders involved in the process (such as the expert behind the TripleA-reno combined label) and gain people's trust by reassuring that the work will worth, showing them their actual position and closeness or distance to potential improvements. By validating comfort ranges established in some of the indicators included in the TripleA-combined performance label on energy, indoor environment and well-being, we proofed its usefulness and adaptation to the pilot buildings, so all participants could see their status.

Almost all the indicators' limits were validated as usable and relatable for the pilot sites, as expected, being them established after a deep search on existing labels and certificates, but two of them stood out for being too tight and too wide respectively: best temperature ranges resulted very difficult to score, and on the contrary, good relative humidity ranges were too easy to score.

Indoor environmental quality and well-being indicators recommendations - In general, one of the main objectives of TripleA-reno is to decouple increased comfort and well-being from an increase in energy consumption. Therefore there was conducted investigation whether there is a relationship between the pairs of variables listed below:

- Energy consumption & Measured Indoor Environmental Quality,
 - Energy Consumption & Perceived Comfort
 - Energy Consumption & Health-related symptoms reported,
 - Energy consumption & Environmental Stressors reported,
- But also,
- Measured Indoor Environmental Quality & Perceived Comfort,
 - Measured Indoor Environmental Quality & Health-related symptoms reported,
 - Measured Indoor Environmental Quality & Environmental Stressors reported.

²¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/784972>

3.15 U-Cert

U-CERT's²² main aim is to introduce a next generation of user-centred Energy Performance Assessment and Certification Scheme to value buildings in a holistic and cost-effective manner.

- Facilitate convergence of quality and reliability, using the set of CEN/ISO EPB standards, enabling a technology neutral approach that is transparently presenting the national and regional choices on a comparable basis.
- Encourage the development and application of holistic user-centred innovative solutions, including the Smart Readiness Indicator for buildings and Indoor Environmental Quality.
- Encourage and support users in decision making (e.g. on deep renovation), nudge for better choices and instil trust by making visible added (building) value, using EPCs.

U-CERT has a focus on strengthening actual implementation of the EPBD by providing and applying insights from a user perspective and creating a level playing field for sharing implementation experience to all involved stakeholders, facilitated and empowered by the EPB Center.

Table 16 KPIs in U-CERT project

IEQ – For the inclusion of new generation performance indicators, EPC-s should be based on dynamic simulations or hourly calculations for energy and room temperatures, otherwise the IEQ performance and power assessment would not be possible to conduct additional simulations, basically with the extent of another EPC would be needed. However, in many countries, EPC-s for new buildings are already simulated with commercial dynamic simulation tools or with simplified hourly tools, in which cases an involvement of new performance indicators could be seen as natural development step.

- IEQ indicators are generally divided into 3-4 categories, such as thermal comfort, air quality, acoustics, visual comfort etc.
- These indicators are mainly applicable for new buildings – design documentation should include the IEQ criteria to which the building was designed along with relevant calculation or simulation results and measurements where necessary.
- Some of the data required for IEQ assessment is already present in EPCs of selected countries. Such data are ventilation rates, heating and cooling setpoints and cooling system data. Based on this existing data, general thermal comfort, air quality and noise categories can be easily determined while local thermal discomfort assessment would be typically needed to determine the category of thermal comfort comprehensively and reliably.
- Complete IEQ assessment requires typically some additional design tasks and competence of the designer/assessor.

These additional design tasks should collect information about air distribution to assess air velocities, i.e. to conduct supply air devices jet calculation with relevant software in representative rooms that is very important for occupant comfort and wellbeing because draught complaints are one of the most common complaints in modern offices. In some cases, an additional room temperature and cooling load simulations may also be required, but in many cases, these are already included in the design of HVAC & energy

SRI – SRI indicator may be included in Power Indicators scheme.

Power Indicators (describing peak and typical loads of the building on electricity, DH and cooling grids and networks) – Current EPCs consider only the energy expenditure of the building, while the power needs are completely neglected. Existing energy performance minimum requirements may lead to situation where buildings with similar energy expenditures, but different power profiles may cause highly different load for the corresponding distribution grids (electricity, district heating, district

²² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/839937>

cooling) in a contrasting manner. Energy flexibility is an issue raised by Smart Readiness Indicator, but is currently not addressed in any EPC:

- Responding to the grid demand and supply allows for (peak) power shifting, as well as using alternative means of energy production or storage, e.g. renewables if available onsite.
- It is expected that some flexibility indicators could be developed under the Smart Readiness Indicator assessment, where grid flexibility and demand-response are evaluated parameters.

Starting point for flexibility indicators can be simple delivered and exported energy duration curves with hourly data by energy carrier which help to describe the effect of the building on distribution grids:

- More flexibility indicators may be developed within the SRI framework.
- Simple and robust power indicator is to consider the (5th/95th percentile of hourly peak power loads W/m^2) of delivered and exported energy.

3.16 X-tendo

X-tendo²³ and its toolbox introduce ten features of the next generation of energy performance certificates, to provide public authorities with improved compliance, reliability, usability and convergence of next-generation energy performance assessment and certification.

The main tool to support public officers is the X-tendo toolbox, which considers the strengths and weaknesses of current EPC schemes according to their effect on the market, end users and the society as a whole, and looks into possible additions and improvements to these schemes. The modular structure of the toolbox covers unique features of innovative indicators as well as innovative data handling approaches. The features are smart readiness indicator, comfort, outdoor air pollution, real energy consumption, district heating, EPC databases, building logbook, tailored recommendations, financing options, one stop shops. A selection of relevant test projects will demonstrate the potential of the developed toolbox to deliver more reliable next-generation EPC schemes across the EU. By enhancing innovative aspects in the X-tendo toolbox and disseminating the toolbox throughout Europe, the innovative aspects will gain ground in a quick and effortless way. The modular structure also enables energy agencies to choose for a gradual implementation of all aspects, as it ensures the possibility of a stepwise innovation of EPC schemes, without risking lock-in effects as all the modules of the toolbox can interoperate.

Table 17 KPIs in X-tendo project

SRI - Method A will be considered as the reference SRI assessment method within the Xtendo project. This is because it has equivalent outputs when compared to the more detailed method B together with a reduced assessment time.

Not all buildings are evaluated equally. Different building parameters (type, characteristics, geographical location) will determine the eligible assessment facets (theoretical maximum) as well as the weighted values of each.

The final SRI score is provided in the form of a percentage and subdivided in three subcategories matching EPBD objectives: "energy savings & maintenance", "comfort, ease & well-being" and "grid flexibility".

Comfort (thermal comfort and indoor air quality) - Most of the existing systems focus on granting rankings based on extensive criteria (e.g. technical, verification, measurements and assessments), generally with longer monitoring time requirements for evaluation (e.g. monthly/annual). The assessment of comfort for EPCs should be done in a relatively shorter time and with less effort to reduce the cost of assessment and increase the affordability for the end-user (cost is a big barrier for many households). The assessment methods would consist of checklists

²³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/845958>

(observations/measurements), surveys and on-site monitoring depending on the requirements of the individual parameter. The approach will be developed to keep the assessments adaptable, affordable and time effective. Four main indicators will be assessed within the comfort feature:

- thermal comfort,
- indoor air quality,
- visual comfort,
- acoustic comfort.

To identify the overall IEQ level, all four indicators will be assessed independently based on multiple criteria with differing weightages assigned to them. Under each criterion, certain parameters must be met to achieve a required score. The score will be awarded using the relevant assessment method (e.g. checklist, survey, monitoring etc.). A combined rating with a single value will give an overall idea of the indoor environment but will not specify the problem areas and there is a greater chance of making errors in applying corrective measures. Therefore, an individual rating for all four indicators is proposed to provide more details for interventions.

Outdoor air pollution - The proposed method considers fuel combustion in the building for the purpose of heat and electricity generation for the functions included in the national EPC system. In the local air pollution contributor index assessment method, the calculated building emissions will be compared with reference emissions and for each pollutant an index level will be assigned. Using the value of building energy consumption and the type of energy source (type of fuel) the building emission indicators (PM10, PM2.5, NO_x, SO_x, CO) are calculated. Next, the reference emission indicators are calculated using reference energy consumption and reference energy source. The reference values will be estimated based on national regulations. Using calculated values, the ratio of building to reference emission indicators will be estimated (ratio of emission indicator). The ratio of each pollutant will be assessed using a scale (very low, low, moderate, high, very high, hazardous). The indexes (index of emission indicator) show the impact of a given pollutant on outdoor air pollution in comparison with reference values. A very low index means that pollutant emissions from the assessed building are much lower than for the reference building, meaning the contribution of the building to local smog development is very low. In the last step, the pollutant indexes are weighted to get one value for the local air pollution contributor index.

Real energy consumption - Two approaches were identified as candidates most suitable for inclusion in EPC schemes. Within each approach category, one best option method was suggested for further elaboration:

- Building-level simple approach.
- Building-level detailed approach: whole building heat loss coefficient (HLC).

More enhanced detailed building- and district-level approaches will become available in the future, but more research is necessary to fine-tune the combinations of measurement set-up and analysis methods in relation to the accuracy requirements and cost and time constraints. The second method (HLC) was also evaluated to be currently not feasible for inclusion in EPC schemes for similar reasons. It is the most promising method of buildinglevel detailed approaches, and with some limited further research (for e.g. automation of procedure) will be ready for cost-effective implementation in EPC schemes in a future context of broad-scale sensor deployment and increasing availability of data.

The building-level simple approach method combines features that are included in the initial selection of options for methods and indicators identified as suitable for including real energy consumption in EPCs. Building-level simple approach method for the determination of energy performance based on real energy consumption.

The method requires measurement infrastructure for monitoring of all energy constituents and per energy carrier. Only the domestic hot water use monitoring can be replaced by using a calculation model. If only billing energy consumption information is available, normalisation options are limited and in most cases modules for calculated energy consumption are used to complete the missing data, such as for the implementation of the heating degree day method. The output is an energy performance indicator, the "energy use indicator", representing the yearly specific primary energy consumption of the building. Normalisation or correction of the indicator to standard consumption or external conditions is included for:

- Size of the building unit (floor area).
- External weather conditions (heating and cooling degree days method).
- Energy carrier (primary energy factors).

It is optional for:

- Indoor thermal comfort level (inclusion in HDD/CDD).
- Indoor air quality level.
- Service provision.

The inclusion of an additional optional indicator of share of renewable energy and of additional optional user behaviour benchmarking can be considered.

District energy - The estimated future performance of each district heating system should be expressed via the PEF, REF and CEF for a future point in time. Based on estimated future balancing data (plant capacities, full load hours, CO₂ factors of electricity) and a roadmap for implementation. The calculation should then be approved by a recognised association or authority. In the EPC, these values can be used to express future primary energy, renewable energy, and CO₂ emissions of the building or for calculating tailored recommendations.

The input data and information needed for the calculation distinguishing between heat generation, heat distribution and the public electricity grid. Assumptions have to be made for all of these values reflecting a predefined future year.

The heat distribution and transfer system of a building should be characterised by the necessary supply line temperature and the expectable return temperature. Both values should represent temperatures at the supply side for a central heat supply system, even if such a system is not currently in place. The basis for the calculation is the necessary heat load of the building. Via the available heat transfer area in the building, the maximum temperature at the end of the supply line is calculated. The temperature losses in the heat distribution system are then estimated via the isolation, length and location of the supply lines. The temperature reduction in the return line, on the other hand, is estimated based on the existing control system of the heat distribution system.

4 KPIs in partner countries

Understanding the performance indicators in the project partner countries is necessary. This section describes the main key performance indicators (KPIs) and the different energy classes within our project. The first page of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) serves as our guiding framework, directing attention to the initial stages of the assessment.

This chapter analyzes the KPIs from the first page of the energy performance certificate. The first page of an EPC is usually the main thing users pay attention to. It should contain the most important KPIs, energy classes and other information important to the user.

As mentioned in introduction all KPIs are grouped in 5 categories: Smartness (yellow), Human-Centric (blue), Energy performance (green), Financial (pink), Climate change (red)

4.1 Austria

Figure 2 Front page of the Austrian EPC

The main indicators in the Austrian EPC are:

Reference heat energy demand (HWB _{Ref})
Primary energy demand (PEB)
Total equivalent carbon dioxide emissions (greenhouse gases) (CO _{2,EPK})
Total energy efficiency factor (f _{REF})
Hot water heating demand (WWWB)
Heating energy demand (HEB)

Household electricity demand (HHSB)
Operating electricity demand (BSB) in case of non-residential buildings
Cooling energy demand (KEB) in case of non-residential buildings
End energy demand (EEB)

The reference heat energy demand (HWB_{Ref}), the primary energy demand (PEB), total equivalent carbon dioxide emissions (greenhouse gases) (CO_{2eq}) and the total energy efficiency factor (f_{GEE}) are shown on the front page in scale from A++ to G.

Klasse	$HWB_{Ref,SK}$ [kWh/m ² a]	PEB_{SK} [kWh/m ² a]	$CO_{2eq,SK}$ [kg/m ² a]	$f_{GEE,SK}$ [-]
A++	10	60	8	0,55
A+	15	70	10	0,70
A	25	80	15	0,85
B	50	160	30	1,00
C	100	220	40	1,75
D	150	280	50	2,50
E	200	340	60	3,25
F	250	400	70	4,00
G	> 250	> 400	> 70	> 4,00

Figure 3 Austrian energy classes.

4.2 Bulgaria

СЕРТИФИКАТ

за енергийни характеристики на сграда в експлоатация

Номер		СТРАДА С БЛИЗКО ДО НУЛАТА ПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕ НА ЕНЕРГИЯ	ДА <input type="checkbox"/>	Дал на потребяемата възобновяема енергия за отопление, охлаждане, вентилация, БГВ и осветление	... %
Валиден до:		НЕ <input type="checkbox"/>			

(сграда или част от сграда, жилищен обект, адрес)

Идентификатор (по смисъла на ЗКИР):

Характеристики на сградата		Нормализирано потребление на първична енергия	
		Вид енергия	Общо kWh/год.
Година на първоначално въвеждане в експлоатация	Първична невъзобновяема енергия
Разгъната застроена площ m ²	Първична възобновяема енергия
Обща климатизирана площ m ²	Първична енергия - обща
Общ климатизиран обем m ³	Изнесена възобновяема енергия

EP _{норм} kWh/m ²	EP kWh/m ²	EP _{норм} kWh/m ²	Многофункционална жилава на отажд./охлаждае - окала на енергопотребление по възобновяема първична енергия	EP първична ЕСМ kWh/m ²	EP след ЕСМ kWh/m ²
0	EP <	90	A		
90	≤ EP <	180	B		70
180	≤ EP <	235	C		
235	≤ EP <	290	D		245
290	≤ EP <	363	E		
363	≤ EP <	435	F		
435	≤ EP		G		

Потребна енергия, генерирани емисии CO ₂ и дял на възобновяемата енергия					
Потребна енергия в нормализирано състояние	...	MWh/год.			
Генерирани емисии CO ₂ в нормализирано/ базово състояние	...	тона/год.			
Генерирани емисии CO ₂ след ЕСМ	...	тона/год.			
Дял на първичната възобновяема енергия в нормализирано състояние	...	%			
Дял на първичната възобновяема енергия след ЕСМ	...	%			

РАЗПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ НА ГОДИШНОТО ПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕ НА ПОТРЕБНА ЕНЕРГИЯ					
Отопление	Вентилация	Охлаждане	Гореща вода	Осветление	Уреди
... %	... %	... %	... %	... %	... %

Срок на освобождаване от данък сгради по ЗМДТ от xx.xx.xxxx г. до xx.xx.xxxx г.	Издаден от (наименование на юридическото лице) (име, фамилия на управителя) Регистрационен номер № / г. (подпис, печат)
Издаден на	

Figure 4 Front page of the Bulgarian EPC

The main indicators in the Bulgarian EPC are:

Share of renewable energy demand for heating, cooling, ventilation, DHW and lighting [%]
Primary non-renewable energy [kWh/m ² , kWh/year]
Primary renewable energy [kWh/m ² , kWh/year]
Primary energy - total [kWh/m ² , kWh/year]
Exported renewable energy [kWh/year]
Energy consumption in normalized state [MWh/year]
Generated CO ₂ emissions at normalized condition [tCO ₂ /year]
Generated CO ₂ emissions after energy saving measures [tCO ₂ /year]
Share of the primary renewable energy at normalized condition [%]
Share of the primary renewable energy after energy saving measures [%]
Distribution of annual energy consumption [%]

Energy classes for new buildings in Bulgaria are determined on the basis of the primary energy index with the following values:

Table 18 Bulgarian primary energy consumption scale

EP_{min} kWh/m ²	EP kWh/m ²	EP_{max} kWh/m ²	Energy class rating
0	EP <	90	A
90	≤ EP <	180	B
180	≤ EP <	235	C
235	≤ EP <	290	D
290	≤ EP <	363	E
363	≤ EP <	435	F
435	≤ EP		G

Two indicators are classified, primary energy before implementation of energy saving measures and after implementation.

4.3 Croatia

ENERGETSKI CERTIFIKAT ZGRADE
prema Pravilniku o energetskom pregledu zgrade i energetskom certifikiranju (Narodne novine 88/2017)

Srednja škola Bedekovčina
Nova zgrada

Nova samostalna uporabna dijelna zgrada
Gajeva 1 **49221** **Bedekovčina**
Ulica i kvart broj Poštanski broj Mjesto

PODACI O ZGRADI	<input type="checkbox"/> nova	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> postojeća	<input type="checkbox"/> rekonstrukcija
Vrsta zgrade (prema Pravilniku)	Zgrade za obrazovanje		
Vrsta zgrade prema složenosti tehničkih sustava	zgrada sa složenim tehničkim sustavom		
Vlasnik / Investitor	Krapinsko zagorska županija		
k.č.br.	5733/1	k.o.	Bedekovčina
Ploščina korisne površine grijanog dijela zgrade A _k [m ²]	3.765,81	Godina izgradnje / rekonstrukcije	1957 / 2020
Gradevinska (bruto) površina zgrade [m ²]	4.179,00	Mjerska meteorološka postaja	STUBIČKE TOPLICE
Faktor oblika f ₀ [m ⁻¹]	0,45	Referencna klima	Kontinentalna

ENERGETSKI RAZRED ZGRADE	Specifična godišnja potrebna toplinska energija za grijanje Q _{h,nd} [kWh/(m ² a)]	Specifična godišnja primarna energija E _{prim} [kWh/(m ² a)]
	52	73
	C	C
Specifična godišnja isporučena energija E _{del} [kWh/(m ² a)]	64	
Specifična godišnja emisija CO ₂ [kg/(m ² a)]	14	
<small>Upisati: "n20" ako energetsko svojstvo zgrade (E_{prim}) zadovoljava zahtjeve za zgrade gotovo nulte energije propisane važećim TPRIJETZ2</small>		

ROK VAŽENJA CERTIFIKATA / PODACI O OSOBI KOJA JE IZDALA ENERGETSKI CERTIFIKAT			
Oznaka energetskog certifikata	P_387_2013_10299_NS2	Datum izdavanja	25.9.2020.
Datum važenja	25.9.2030.		
Ime i prezime imenarice/osobe izdavalke	KENDL BAU j.d.o.o.	Registarski broj	P-387/2013
Ime i prezime imenarice/osobe izdavalke (prema pravilniku) osobe ili ime i prezime ovlaštene fizičke osobe /vlastoručni potpis	Vanja Kekez dipl. ing. građ. Vanja Kekez dipl. ing. građ. Oblasni inženjer građevinarstva	KENDL BAU j.d.o.o. Zagreb	

PODACI O OSOBAMA KOJE SU SUDJELOVALE U IZRADI ENERGETSKOG CERTIFIKATA			
Diz. zgrade	Ime i prezime ovlaštene osobe	Naziv pravne osobe	Registarski broj
Gradevinski	Vanja Kekez dipl. ing. građ.	KENDL BAU j.d.o.o.	P-387/2013
Strojarski	Ivan Kucas dipl. ing. stroj.		F-314/2011
Elektrotehnički	Zdenko Tica dipl. ing. el.	ZN-TICA d.o.o.	P-895/2013

Figure 5 Front page of the Croatian EPC

The main indicators in the Croatian EPC are:

Specific annual heat energy requirements for heating (Q _{h,nd}) [kWh/(m ² a)]
Specific annual primary energy (E _{prim}) [kWh/(m ² a)]
Specific annual delivered energy (E _{del}) [kWh/(m ² year)]
Specific annual CO ₂ emission [kg/(m ² year)]

nZEB rating, if the energy performance of the building (E_{prim}) meets the requirement for nearly zero-energy buildings prescribed by the applicable Technical Regulation on rational use of energy and thermal protection in Buildings (TPRUETZZ)

Determination of energy classes of a particular type of building is based on a specific annual necessary energy for heating $Q_{H,nd}$ for reference climate data and Algorithm prescribed operating regime technical systems:

Energetski razred	Specifična godišnja potrebna toplinska energija za grijanje $Q''_{H,nd}$ [kWh/(m ² a)]
A+	≤ 15
A	≤ 25
B	≤ 50
C	≤ 100
D	≤ 150
E	≤ 200
F	≤ 250
G	> 250

Figure 6 Croatian energy classes

For each of the above types of buildings and individual energy classes (A+, A, B, C, D, E, F, G) is in Annex 1 Ordinance on energy audit of buildings and energy certification states the area of specific primary energy values in [kWh/(m²a)]:

E_{prim} (kWh/m ² a)	STAMBENA		OBITELJSKA		UREDSKA		OBRAZOVNA		BOLNICA		HOTEL I RESTORAN		SPORTSKA DVORANA		TRGOVINA		OSTALE NESTAMBENE	
	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P	K	P
A+	≤ 80	≤ 50	≤ 45	≤ 35	≤ 35	≤ 25	≤ 55	≤ 55	≤ 250	≤ 250	≤ 90	≤ 70	≤ 210	≤ 150	≤ 170	≤ 150	≤ 80	≤ 50
A	> 80	> 50	> 45	> 35	> 35	> 25	> 55	> 55	> 250	> 250	> 90	> 70	> 210	> 150	> 170	> 150	> 80	> 50
	≤ 100	≤ 75	≤ 80	≤ 55	≤ 55	≤ 50	≤ 60	≤ 58	≤ 275	≤ 275	≤ 110	≤ 75	≤ 305	≤ 160	≤ 310	≤ 210	≤ 115	≤ 75
B	> 100	> 75	> 80	> 55	> 55	> 50	> 60	> 58	> 275	> 275	> 110	> 75	> 305	> 160	> 310	> 210	> 115	> 75
	≤ 120	≤ 90	≤ 115	≤ 70	≤ 70	≤ 70	≤ 65	≤ 60	≤ 300	≤ 300	≤ 130	≤ 80	≤ 400	≤ 170	≤ 450	≤ 280	≤ 150	≤ 100
C	> 120	> 90	> 115	> 70	> 70	> 70	> 65	> 60	> 300	> 300	> 130	> 80	> 400	> 170	> 450	> 280	> 150	> 100
	≤ 265	≤ 220	≤ 280	≤ 230	≤ 100	≤ 90	≤ 125	≤ 120	≤ 345	≤ 325	≤ 160	≤ 95	≤ 465	≤ 225	≤ 475	≤ 290	≤ 280	≤ 225
D	> 265	> 220	> 280	> 230	> 100	> 90	> 125	> 120	> 345	> 325	> 160	> 95	> 465	> 225	> 475	> 290	> 280	> 225
	≤ 410	≤ 350	≤ 445	≤ 385	≤ 125	≤ 110	≤ 175	≤ 175	≤ 395	≤ 350	≤ 190	≤ 110	≤ 530	≤ 280	≤ 495	≤ 340	≤ 410	≤ 350
E	> 410	> 350	> 445	> 385	> 125	> 110	> 175	> 175	> 395	> 350	> 190	> 110	> 530	> 280	> 495	> 340	> 410	> 350
	≤ 515	≤ 435	≤ 560	≤ 485	≤ 155	≤ 140	≤ 220	≤ 220	≤ 495	≤ 440	≤ 240	≤ 140	≤ 665	≤ 350	≤ 620	≤ 425	≤ 515	≤ 435
F	> 515	> 435	> 560	> 485	> 155	> 140	> 220	> 220	> 495	> 440	> 240	> 140	> 665	> 350	> 620	> 425	> 515	> 435
	≤ 615	≤ 520	≤ 670	≤ 580	≤ 190	≤ 165	≤ 265	≤ 265	≤ 590	≤ 525	≤ 290	≤ 165	≤ 795	≤ 415	≤ 745	≤ 510	≤ 615	≤ 520
G	> 615	> 520	> 670	> 580	> 190	> 165	> 265	> 265	> 590	> 525	> 290	> 165	> 795	> 415	> 745	> 510	> 615	> 520

K – kontinentalna Hrvatska, P – primorska Hrvatska

Figure 7 Croatian building types and energy classes

Legend:

- K - Continental Croatia,
- P - Coastal Croatia,
- Stambena - multi-apartment buildings,
- Obiteljska - family houses,
- Uredska - office buildings,
- Obrazovna - education buildings,
- Bolnica - hospitals,

- Hotel i restoran – hotels and restaurants,
- Sportska dvorana – sports halls,
- Trgovina – wholesale and retail buildings
- Ostale nestambene – other non-residential buildings heated to +18°C or higher (e.g. transport and communications buildings, terminals, stations, post offices, telecommunications buildings, buildings for cultural and artistic activity and entertainment, museums, libraries)

4.4 Denmark

Figure 8 Front page of the Danish EPC

The main indicators in the Danish EPC are:

Current energy class
How much the owner overpays for energy per year (if applicable)
Energy consultant recommendations with listed annual money savings and investment price
Energy consumption of the building now and after energy saving measures:

District heating [kr.]
Electricity for other [kr.]
Total energy cost [kr.]
Total CO ₂ emissions [ton]

The Danish DEPCs define labels running on a scale from A to G, where A is divided into four groups:

- A2010 (standard – low energy buildings)
- A2015 (low energy buildings)
- A2020 (zero energy buildings)
- A2020+ (Passive houses)

The scale for residential buildings is indicated below:

Table 19 Danish energy classes

Scale	Limit value in kWh/m ² *year
A2020	27,0
A2015	< 30,0 + 1000/A
A2010	< 52,5 + 1650/A
B	< 70,0 + 2200/A
C	< 110 + 3200/A
D	< 150 + 4200/A
E	< 190 + 5200/A
F	< 240 + 6500/A
G	> 240 + 6500/A

Where A is the heated area in m².

4.5 Greece

ΠΙΣΤΟΠΟΙΗΤΙΚΟ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗΣ ΑΠΟΔΟΣΗΣ (ΠΕΑ)	
Αρ. Προποκάλλου:	Αρ. Ασφαλείας:
Ημερομηνία Έκδοσης: 15/04/2020	Ημερομηνία Ισχύος: 15/04/2030
* Ελέγξτε την εγκυρότητα του ΠΕΑ: https://www.buldingcert.gr/inspectCertView	
Τίτλος Κτηριακής Μονάδας:	
Χρήση:	Πολυκατοικία
Κλιματική Ζώνη:	A
Συνολική Επιφάνεια:	191.843
Οφέλιμη Επιφάνεια:	191.843
Ενεργειακή κατηγορία:	Υφιστάμενη Διηθητική
Μηδενικής Ενεργειακής Κατανάλωσης:	
EP ≤ 0,35 R _{ref}	A+
0,35 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 0,50 R _{ref}	A
0,50 R _{ref} < EP < 0,75 R _{ref}	B+
0,75 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 1,00 R _{ref}	B
1,00 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 1,41 R _{ref}	Γ
1,41 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 1,82 R _{ref}	Δ
1,82 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 2,27 R _{ref}	Ε
2,27 R _{ref} < EP ≤ 2,73 R _{ref}	Ζ
2,73 R _{ref} < EP	Η
* Μετά την εφαρμογή των παρεμβάσεων ενεργειακής αναβάθμισης σύμφωνα με τη μέτρηση (1η στήλη)	
Υπολογιζόμενη ετήσια κατανάλωση πρωτογενούς ενέργειας*	
Κτηρίου αναφοράς [kWh/m ²]:	85,1
Επιθεωρούμενου κτηρίου [kWh/m ²]:	121,8
Πραγματική Ετήσια Κατανάλωση Επιθεωρούμενου Κτηρίου:	
Ηλεκτρικής ενέργειας [kWh/m ²]:	---
Θερμικής ενέργειας (καύσιμα) [kWh/m ²]:	---
Συνολική ετήσια κατανάλωση πρωτογενούς ενέργειας [kWh/m ²]:	---
Ετήσιες εκπομπές CO ₂ επιθεωρούμενου κτηρίου	
Υπολογιζόμενες ετήσιες εκπομπές CO ₂ [kg / m ²]:	41,8
Πραγματικές ετήσιες εκπομπές CO ₂ [kg / m ²]:	---
Θερμική άνεση <input type="checkbox"/>	Οπτική άνεση <input type="checkbox"/>
Ακουστική άνεση <input type="checkbox"/>	Ποιότητα εσωτερικού αέρα <input type="checkbox"/>
* Η ενεργειακή απόδοση ενός κτηρίου προσδιορίζεται βάσει της υπολογιζόμενης ετήσιας κατανάλωσης ενέργειας για την κάλυψη των αναγκών που συνδέονται με τη χρήση του όγκου να επαγγελματικά ανθρώπους θερμικής και οπτικής άνεσης.	

Figure 9 Front page of the Greek EPC

The main indicators in the Greek EPC are:

Current energy class
Energy class after energy saving measures
Estimated annual primary energy consumption:
Reference building [kWh/m ²]
Inspected building [kWh/m ²]
Actual annual consumption of the inspected building
Electricity [kWh/m ²]
Heating (fuel) [kWh/m ²]
Total annual primary energy consumption [kWh/m ²]
Estimated annual CO ₂ emissions [kg / m ²]
Actual annual CO ₂ emissions [kg / m ²]

The energy efficiency classes of buildings in Greece are shown in the table below. The class is assigned using a multiple of the R_R index, where this index is equal to the calculated primary energy consumption of the reference building.

Table 20 Greek non-renewable primary energy consumption scale

EP_{min} [kWh/m ² *year]	EP_{max} [kWh/m ² *year]	Class
-	$\leq 0,33 R_R$	A+
$0,33 R_R <$	$\leq 0,50 R_R$	A
$0,50 R_R <$	$\leq 0,75 R_R$	B+
$0,75 R_R <$	$\leq 1,00 R_R$	B
$1,00 R_R <$	$\leq 1,41 R_R$	Г
$1,41 R_R <$	$\leq 1,82 R_R$	Δ
$1,82 R_R <$	$\leq 2,27 R_R$	E
$2,27 R_R <$	$\leq 2,73 R_R$	Z
$2,73 R_R <$	-	H

A reference building is a residential building that meets the minimum requirements in accordance with Article 8 of the KENAK Ordinance, which new and renovated buildings should meet. The exact technical characteristics of the reference building, including geometric characteristics, location, orientation, and technical characteristics of heating, cooling and ventilation systems, are described in Article 9 of the KENAK Ordinance.

4.6 Malta

Figure 10 Front page of the Malta's EPC

The main indicators in Malta's EPC are:

Energy use [kWh/m ² *year]
Carbon dioxide emissions [kg/m ² *year]

Malta's EPC does not have energy classes, energy consumption is shown on a colour scale from dark green (0 kWh/m²*year) to red (280 kWh/m²*year), the similar colour scale also functions for CO₂ emissions, from light blue (0 kg/m²*year) to dark grey (70 kg/m²*year).

4.7 Poland

WZÓR ŚWIADECTWA CHARAKTERYSTYKI ENERGETYCZNEJ BUDYNKU

ŚWIADECTWO CHARAKTERYSTYKI ENERGETYCZNEJ BUDYNKU			
Numer świadectwa ¹⁾			
Oceniany budynek			
Rodzaj budynku ²⁾		Zdjęcie budynku	
Przeznaczenie budynku ³⁾			
Adres budynku			
Budynek, o którym mowa w art. 3 ust. 2 ustawy ⁴⁾			
Rok oddania do użytkowania budynku ⁵⁾			
Metoda wyznaczania charakterystyki energetycznej ⁶⁾			
Powierzchnia pomieszczeń o regulowanej temperaturze powietrza (powierzchnia ogrzewana lub chłodzona) A_v [m ²] ⁷⁾			
Powierzchnia użytkowa [m ²]			
Ważne do (rrrr-mm-dd)⁸⁾			
Stacja meteorologiczna, według której danych wyznaczana jest charakterystyka energetyczna ⁹⁾			
Ocena charakterystyki energetycznej budynku¹⁰⁾			
Wskaźniki charakterystyki energetycznej	Oceniany budynek	Wymagania dla nowego budynku według przepisów techniczno-budowlanych¹¹⁾	
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na energię użytkową	EU = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na energię końcową ¹²⁾	EK = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na nieodnawialną energię pierwotną ¹²⁾	EP = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)	EP = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)	
Jednostkowa wielkość emisji CO ₂	E _{CO2} = ... t CO ₂ /(m ² · rok)		
Udział odnawialnych źródeł energii w rocznym zapotrzebowaniu na energię końcową	U _{oze} = ... %		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na nieodnawialną energię pierwotną EP [kWh/(m² · rok)] 			
Obliczeniowa roczna ilość zużywanego nośnika energii lub energii przez budynek¹³⁾			
System techniczny	Rodzaj nośnika energii lub energii	Ilość nośnika energii lub energii	Jednostka/(m² · rok)
Ogrzewania	1) n)		
Przygotowania ciepłej wody użytkowej	1) n)		
Chłodzenia	1) n)		
Wbudowanej instalacji oświetlenia ¹⁴⁾	1) n)		

Figure 11 Front page of the Polish EPC

The main indicators in the Polish EPC are:

Index of annual useful energy demand (EU) [kWh/(m ² ·year)]
Index of annual final energy demand (EK) [kWh/(m ² ·year)]
Index of annual demand for non-renewable primary energy (EP) [kWh/(m ² ·year)]
Specific CO ₂ emissions (E _{CO2}) [t CO ₂ /(m ² ·year)]
Share of renewable energy sources in annual final energy demand (U _{oze}) [%].

There are no energy classes in Poland, instead, there is a colour-coded scale on which the indicator of the annual demand for non-renewable primary energy of the assessed building and the required indicator for a new building are marked.

4.8 Slovenia

Figure 12 Front page of the Slovenian EPC

The main indicators in the Slovenian EPC are:

Energy demand for heating A1-G [kWh/(m ² *year)]
Delivered energy for building operation [kWh/(m ² *year)]
Primary energy [kWh/(m ² *year)]
CO ₂ emission [kg/m ² *year]

The energy label classification based on the annual specific energy need for heating in Slovenia is defined in the table below.

Barva	Razred	Letna potrebna toplota na enoto uporabne površine (kWh/m2a)	Opis energijske učinkovitosti stavbe
	A1	od 0 do vključno 10 kWh/m2a	skoraj-nič energijska
	A2	od 10 do vključno 15 kWh/m2a	pasivna
	B1	od 15 do vključno 25 kWh/m2a	nizkoenergijska
	B2	od 25 do vključno 35 kWh/m2a	dobro učinkovita
	C	od 35 do vključno 60 kWh/m2a	zadostno učinkovita
	D	od 60 do vključno 105 kWh/m2a	nezadostno učinkovita
	E	od 105 do vključno 150 kWh/m2a	potratna
	F	od 150 do vključno 210 kWh/m2a	zelo potratna
	G	od 210 do 300 in več kWh/m2a	izjemno potratna

Figure 13 Slovenian EPC energy classes.

4.9 Spain

CERTIFICADO DE EFICIENCIA ENERGÉTICA DE EDIFICIOS

IDENTIFICACIÓN DEL EDIFICIO O DE LA PARTE QUE SE CERTIFICA:

Nombre del edificio		MUSEO ETNOGRÁFICO DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN	
Dirección		SACRAMENTO, 20	
Municipio	Zamora	Código Postal	49004
Provincia	Zamora	Comunidad Autónoma	Castilla y León
Zona climática	D2	Año construcción	2003
Normativa vigente (construcción / rehabilitación)	NBE-CT-79		
Referencia catastral	0785411L79088001HW		

Tipo de edificio o parte del edificio que se certifica:

<input type="radio"/> Edificio de nueva construcción	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Edificio Existente
<input type="radio"/> Vivienda	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Terciano
<input type="radio"/> Unifamiliar	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Edificio completo
<input type="radio"/> Bloque	<input type="radio"/> Local
<input type="radio"/> Bloque completo	
<input type="radio"/> Vivienda individual	

DATOS DEL TÉCNICO CERTIFICADOR:

Nombre y Apellidos	EDUARDO LIEBANA ALONSO	NIF(NIE)	06767820M
Razón social	EDUARDO LIEBANA ALONSO	NIF	06767829M
Domicilio	GONZALO DE BERCEO, 17		
Municipio	TROBAJO DELCAMINO	Código Postal	24009
Provincia	León	Comunidad Autónoma	Castilla y León
e-mail	eliebana@geindus.es	Teléfono	616836020
Titulación habilitante según normativa vigente	INGENIERO TÉCNICO INDUSTRIAL		
Procedimiento reconocido de calificación energética utilizado y versión:	CEXv2.3		

CALIFICACIÓN ENERGÉTICA OBTENIDA:

CONSUMO DE ENERGÍA PRIMARIA NO RENOVABLE [kWh/m² año]	EMISIONES DE DIÓXIDO DE CARBONO [kgCO2/m² año]

El técnico abjso firmante declara responsablemente que ha realizado la certificación energética del edificio o de la parte que se certifica de acuerdo con el procedimiento establecido por la normativa vigente y que son ciertos los datos que figuran en el presente documento, y sus anexos.

Fecha: 04/03/2022

Firma del técnico certificador:

Anexo I. Descripción de las características energéticas del edificio.
Anexo II. Calificación energética del edificio.
Anexo III. Recomendaciones para la mejora de la eficiencia energética.
Anexo IV. Pruebas, comprobaciones e inspecciones realizadas por el técnico certificador.

Registro del Órgano Territorial Competente:

Fecha: 22/03/2022
Ref. Catastral: 0785411L79088001HW

Página 1 de 8

Figure 14 Front page of the Spanish EPC

The main indicators in the Spanish EPC are:

Non-renewable primary energy consumption [kWh/(m²*year)]

Carbon dioxide emissions [kgCO_{2e}/m²*year]

Both non-renewable primary energy consumption [kWh/(m²*year)] and carbon dioxide emissions [kgCO_{2e}/m²*year] are shown on a scale from A-G. The scale values are shown in the table below:

Table 21 Spanish non-renewable primary energy consumption scale

EP _{min} [kWh/m ² *year]	EP _{max} [kWh/m ² *year]	Class
-	<55.21	A
55.21	89.72	B
89.72	138.03	C
138.03	179.44	D
179.44	220.85	E
220.85	276.06	F
276.06<		G

Table 22 Spanish CO₂ emissions scale

CO ₂ emissions min [kgCO _{2e} /m ² *year]	CO ₂ emissions max [kgCO _{2e} /m ² *year]	Class
-	<9.67	A
9.67	15.71	B
15.71	24.18	C
24.18	31.43	D
31.43	38.68	E
38.68	48.35	F
48.35<		G

4.10 UK (Scotland)

Figure 15 Front page of the Scottish EPC

The main indicators in the Scottish EPC are:

Primary Energy Indicator [kWh/m ² *year]
Estimated energy costs for a house for 3 years [£]
Savings over 3 years [£]
Energy Efficiency Rating (current - potential) [A-G]
Environmental Impact (CO ₂) Rating (current - potential) [A-G]
Actions to take to save money and make house more efficient [£]

Scotland has two scales – Energy Efficiency Rating and Environmental Impact (CO₂) Rating

The energy efficiency Rating is calculated using the standard British RdSAP methodology. It calculates energy consumption for heating, hot water, lighting and ventilation, and then applies fuel costs to that energy consumption to get an overall rating for the house. The rating is given on a scale of 1 to 100. The energy rating is calculated using standard usage assumptions. The assessment also uses national weather information to allow comparisons between buildings in various parts of Scotland.

The Environmental Impact Rating of the house is calculated by applying 'carbon factors' for the fuels used to overall energy use. Carbon factors depend on what fuel is used because different fuels produce different amounts of carbon dioxide for every kilowatt hour (kWh) of energy used.

Both scales are shown in the table below:

Table 23 Scottish EPC's scale

Score	Rating
92+	A
81-91	B
69-80	C
55-68	D
39-54	E
21-38	F
1-20	G

5 Conclusion

There are several approaches observed throughout European-funded projects. The predominant focus of these projects lies in the refinement and adaptation of existing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through conducted research and surveys. Primarily, considerable attention is directed towards KPIs related to the smartness and energy efficiency of buildings. SRI indicator is a quite recent update in European methodology, therefore a lot of projects try to work around this new concept. Notably there is a span of 20 KPIs specifically tailored to assess the energy performance of a building, rendering it the most extensively covered category. It is worth noting that certain projects are still in progress, consequently impeding the availability of publicly accessible information regarding their KPI findings.

At the moment, the most popular indicators are the KPIs from the "energy performance" category, with a total of 44 on the first page of the EPC in the countries. The second most popular category is the indicators from the "climate change" category. - each of them related to CO₂ emissions. The third most popular were financial KPIs - 8 to be exact. "Smartness" and "human-centric" indicators were missing from the front page - this may be due to developing indicators in these categories. SRI will most likely be introduced by the EPBD update.

The largest number of indicators on the front page includes the EPCs of Bulgaria and Greece - 11 each. The smallest are Spain and Malta, with 2 each. Financial KPIs are found only in Denmark (5) and the UK (3). Poland and Malta are the only countries that do not have energy classes labelled as letters, only a colour scale.

As the Energy Performance Certificate is a document that determines the amount of energy required to meet the energy needs associated with the use of a building or part of a building, it is obvious that the vast majority of the KPIs present on the front page of the EPC are from the 'Energy Performance' category. The aim is to promote energy-efficient construction and raise public awareness of the potential for energy savings in buildings, which is well illustrated by the indicators related to a building's CO₂ emissions.

However, it is important to consider whether the plethora of KPIs serves the end user (the building owner/user) or is only readable by assessors and officials who can use the EPC for statistical and technical purposes. The EPC examples from Denmark and Scotland show a human-centred approach, with most of the page devoted to explaining the data, thus making the EPC more readable and likely to lead to real implementation of recommended improvements. EPCs should include a legend or guide on how the values should be read, the most important data presented should be highlighted in text or graphically (e.g. by introducing iconographies).

Each of the five categories of KPIs is important and should be considered together rather than separately. Users would benefit from combining information on energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, comfort, intelligence, financing and recommendations, so that the EPC could be considered as a single, holistic document, conveying full knowledge of the building rather than just a shred of information.

Additional recommendations include:

- promoting real-time data integration within EPC frameworks to enhance the reliability and relevance of energy performance evaluations
- promoting smart-home technologies and calculations based on real energy consumption
- ensuring that Human-Centric KPIs are incorporated into EPC assessments to enhance occupant well-being alongside energy efficiency
- strengthening financial KPIs by promoting transparent and accessible financial analysis tools that support investment decisions and databases
- enhancing alignment with sustainability frameworks such as Level(s) to improve climate impact assessments and contribute to EU climate goals.

Partner countries' Energy Performance Certificates and their contained indicators were tested and documented as part of Deliverable D2.5. This testing adhered to the crossCert methodology, ensuring consistency and comparability across projects.

Following a comprehensive analysis, several projects were selected for 2nd and 3rd round of cross-testing: E-DYCE, EPC Recast, D^2EPC, ePANACEA, EUB-Superhub, TIMEPAC, iBRoad2EPC, U-CERT, QualDeEPC, and X-Tendo. The selection criteria focused on the availability of information and tools, the innovation of proposed indicators, and their geographical applicability. The findings from this exercise were divided into two reports:

Deliverable D2.6 presents the methods and results of cross-testing the first wave of new Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) approaches made available since the project's inception. These primarily include methodologies and procedures developed by EU2020 projects: U-CERT, QualDeEPC, and X-tendo. Meanwhile, Deliverable D2.7 details the cross-testing of data from the second generation of new EPCs, showcasing tests and conclusions from later EU2020 projects.

The evaluation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in the cross-testing exercise highlighted significant advancements introduced by the U-CERT and QualDeEPC projects. The U-CERT project, for instance, proposed an infographic-based approach to represent the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) and Thermal Score in EPCs. This approach was well-received for enhancing the comprehensibility of complex indicators. To improve this system, crossCert partners suggested adding scale limits, integrating detailed textual explanations, and providing supplementary online resources. A standardized color scale (red to green) was recommended to maintain consistency with existing energy rating systems.

QualDeEPC's approach focused on individualized assessments of building components and technical systems. Its use of a traffic light system for efficiency ratings proved to be user-friendly, making renovation priorities easier to identify. The structured assessment principles of QualDeEPC were considered feasible for integration into national EPC formats.

Despite the benefits of new indicators such as the Thermal Score and SRI, their complexity can hinder end-user understanding. Therefore, combining infographics with textual descriptions and standardized scales is recommended for improved accessibility. The structured assessment approach of QualDeEPC and the visual enhancements of U-CERT have shown potential to improve national EPC frameworks, and crossCert partners have emphasized the practical benefits of incorporating these elements.

The X-tendo project's evaluation of the Smart Readiness Indicator revealed that the SRI score shows a low correlation with the energy rating, as these metrics assess different aspects of building performance. While this distinction is understandable by trained professionals, it may cause confusion among end-users. However, crossCert partners concluded that EPC issuers could likely perform SRI assessments using the abbreviated method without additional training, though some training is still advisable.

To enhance user perception and understanding of the SRI, communication campaigns, case studies, incentives, clearer links to Building Management Systems, and simplification of the SRI evaluation process are recommended. Additionally, X-tendo's Comfort Asset Rating Procedure (CARP) demonstrated a weak correlation between energy ratings and comfort metrics, as these metrics address different aspects of building performance. While CARP effectively represents building comfort, its relevance varies by [region](#) climate and its credibility may be affected by user perception. The integration of CARP into EPCs is feasible, but economic factors remain the primary drivers for renovations.

The iBRoad2EPC project aimed to create a Building Renovation Passport (BRP), but testing was not possible due to the unavailability of the tool. Instead, the project's graphical appearance, modular approach, and methodology were evaluated and compared to the D²EPC approach. The D²EPC tool automates the determination of renovation activities based on turnaround time, whereas iBRoad2EPC relies on BRP issuers to establish renovation priorities.

Challenges arose when testing the D²EPC tool due to the requirement of a Building Information Model (BIM). Its success heavily depends on the quality of the model, which, if incomplete, complicates data editing and validation. From a scalability and cost-effectiveness perspective, automation can reduce the need for human resources, but the iBRoad2EPC approach remains more comprehensive and tailored.

E-DYCE's methodology, based on dynamic building calculations, requires real data on building energy consumption, often collected through installed sensors. Limited access to data and the platform prevented full evaluation of its applicability across partner countries.

The ePANACEA project aimed to address gaps in existing EPC schemes, such as the mismatch between theoretical and actual energy consumption, limited smart technology integration, and insufficient user awareness. The project developed a comprehensive methodology involving Methods M1, M2, and M3, although Method 3 proved too complex for immediate use. Testing of Methods M1 and M2, conducted without formal training, underscored the importance of providing manuals and training resources.

The EUB SuperHub aimed to create a certification system based on the Level(s) methodology, offering a virtual one-stop shop through a web platform. However, the platform is still under development and unavailable for testing.

The TIMEPAC project promoted a continuous data flow approach to energy certification, covering the building lifecycle from design to operation. While its guidelines offered valuable recommendations, they were not considered testable products due to their reliance on specialized resources and software.

The EPC Recast project sought to improve EPC reliability through better data collection, model calibration, and quality checks. However, most of its proposed tools were unavailable for testing, and the BIMEO tool required specialized training and equipment, limiting its applicability.

In conclusion, many KPIs from various projects remain difficult to assess due to limited public information, inaccessible platforms, or incompatibility with national conditions. Where access to platforms exists, the requirement for specialized data (such as BIM models, building sensor data, and energy consumption invoices) presents additional challenges. While the next-generation KPIs align with the European Union's goal of achieving zero-emission construction, their widespread application may only be feasible after extensive building thermo-modernization, installation of real-time energy consumption monitoring sensors and the implementation of mandatory online documentation (e.g. logbooks).

6 References

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